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Sustainable production of FeSiB phase change material (PCM) for thermal energy storage

An LCA study

Master's thesis in Materials Science and Engineering

Supervisor: Merete Tangstad

Co-supervisor: Angela Daniela La Rosa

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Norwegian University of Science and Technology
Faculty of Natural Sciences
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Preface

This thesis presents the work which constitutes the deliverable to TMT4920 - Materials Technology, Master's Thesis. I started working for this project summer 2022 as a summer job, doing mapping of the raw materials that would be used. The presented parts of the project started in autumn 2022 as a part of the course TMT4500 - Materials Technology, Specialization Project. The project was continued and finalised with this thesis in June 2023.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation under grant agreement 101057954. The project was conducted as part of the EU project THERMOBAT and aims to find the environmental impact of different production routes for production of a Fe-24Si-11B alloy, which will be used for thermal energy storage.

First, I'd like to thank my supervisor Merete Tangstad for the opportunity to work in this project and her valuable guidance in the metallurgical aspects of the thesis. This project has given me multiple opportunities and memories.

I would also like to thank my co-supervisor Angela Daniela La Rosa for her guidance and tutoring in LCA. She has also given me opportunities beyond that of the project, which I am very grateful for. I look forward to our future collaborations.

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My thesis would not be complete without proofreading. I would like to acknowledge my mom, Anne Lise Pettersen Helåsen for checking all of my tables and figures, as well as Børge A. Kristoffersen and Lise Sørfohn for proofreading my thesis.

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Abstract

The eutectic Fe-24Si-11B alloy is studied for thermal energy storage as part of the EU project THERMOBAT. Three different methods have been created for producing this alloy, named FeSi, FeB, and FeSiAl route in this study. A life cycle assessment (LCA) was conducted to evaluate the environmental impacts of these methods, and to highlight which part of the process has the highest impact.

The functional unit was set to be the production of 1 kg Fe-24Si-11B alloy. The three production methods were compared to find the route with the lowest environmental impact. A comparison between Norway and Spain, two countries where production is likely to take place, was also conducted. Additionally, possible solution for further reducing the impacts were suggested. The impact assessment methods used were CML-IA baseline, ReCiPe 2016 Endpoint (H) and IPCC 2021 GWP. All impact categories were used, but global warming potential (GWP) was studied in more detail.

It was found that the FeB route using primary Al had the highest impact in all categories, and was not the best option for production. A hypothetical route where primary Al was substituted with scrap Al had better results and were more comparable with the other two production methods. Still, the FeB method using scrap Al had a higher impact than the FeSi and FeSiAl route in most categories. FeSiAl turned out to have the lowest impact in almost all of the impact categories.

Studying the GWP found that Norway had impacts of 2.65, 2.25, and 1.65 kg CO₂ eq for FeSi, FeB using scrap Al, and FeSiAl routes, respectively, using the IPCC method. For Spain, the values were 3.38, 2.93, and 2.11 kg CO₂ eq. CML method gave slightly lower results than the IPCC. This means FeSiAl had the lowest GWP.

Norway had a lower impact than Spain, due to the electricity consumption being from hydropower which has lower impact than fossil fuels in Spain. Production taking place in Norway will reduce the impact. Other ways to reduce impact would be to swap fossil fuels for biofuels, replace virgin materials with scrap or recycled materials, and implementing CO₂ capture and energy recovery.

Sammendrag

Den eutektiske Fe-24Si-11B legeringen blir studert for termisk energilagring som en del av EU-prosjektet THERMOBAT. Tre forskjellige metoder har blitt laget for å produsere legering og har blitt kalt FeSi-, FeB-, og FeSiAl-rutene i dette studiet. En livssykel analyse (LCA) ble gjennomført for å evaluere miljøpåvirkningene til disse metodene og for å fremheve hvilke deler av prosessene som har høyest påvirkning.

Den funksjonelle enheten ble satt til å være produksjon av 1 kg Fe-24Si-11B legering. De tre produksjonsmetodene ble sammenlignet for å finne ruten med minst miljøpåvirkning. En sammenligning mellom Norge og Spania, to av landene hvor prosessen er sannsynlig å foregå, ble også gjennomført. I tillegg har mulige løsninger for å videre redusere miljøpåvirkningene blitt foreslått. Methodene for å vurdere miljøpåvirkningene brukt var CML-IA baseline, ReCiPe 2016 Endpoint (H) og IPCC 2021 GWP. Alle kategoriene for miljøpåvirkning ble brukt, men potensial for global oppvarming (GWP) ble vektlagt og studert i mer detalj.

Det ble funnet at FeB ruten med bruk av primær aluminium (Al) hadde høyest miljøpåvirkning i alle kategoriene, og var ikke den beste muligheten for produksjon. En hypotetisk rute hvor primær Al ble byttet ut med Al skrap hadde bedre resultater og var mer sammenlignbar med de to andre produksjonsmetodene. FeB ruten med Al skrap hadde likevel høyere miljøpåvirkning enn FeSi og FeSiAl rutene i de fleste av kategoriene. FeSiAl viste seg å ha den laveste miljøpåvirkningen i de fleste av kategoriene.

Ved studie av GWP ble det funnet at Norge hadde miljøpåvirkning med verdier 2.65, 2.25 og 1.65 kg CO₂ ekvivalent, for hhv. FeSi, FeB med Al skrap og FeSiAl rutene ved IPCC-metoden. For Spania ble verdiene funnet til å være 3.38, 2.93 og 2.11 kg CO₂ ekvivalent. CML-metoden ga litt lavere resultater enn IPCC-metoden. Fra dette kan det sees at FeSiAl hadde lavest GWP.

Norge hadde lavere miljøpåvirkning enn Spania. Dette skyldes at det elektriske forbruket kommer fra vannkraft som har lavere påvirkning enn fossile brensel som blir bruk i Spania. Dette gjør at produksjon i Norge vil redusere miljøpåvirkningene. Andre måter å redusere påvirkningene er å bytte fossile brensel med biobrensel, bytte virgin-materiale med skrap eller resirkulert materiale og å implementere CO₂ fangere og energigjenvinning.

Abbreviations

Abbreviations

- **ES** Spain
- **GHG** Green house gases
- **GWP** Global warming potential
- **GWP100a** Global warming potential for 100 years
- **LCA** Life cycle assessment
- **LHTES** Latent heat thermal energy storage
- **NTNU** Norwegian University of Science and Technology
- **MG-Si** Metallurgical grade silicon
- **NO** Norway
- **ODP** Ozone layer depletion
- **PCM** Phase change material
- **SHTES** Sensible heat thermal energy storage
- **SSB** Statistisk sentralbyrå
- **T.A.N.** Technical ammonium nitrate
- **TES** Thermal energy storage
- **TR** Turkey

Chemical compounds

- **Al** Aluminium
- **Al₂O₃** Aluminium oxide, also known as alumina

-
- **As** Arsenic
 - **B** Boron
 - **B₂O₃** Boron oxide
 - **B₄C** Boron carbide
 - **C** Carbon
 - **Ca** Calcium
 - **Ca₂B₆O₅·5H₂O**
 - **CaCO₃** Calcium carbonate
 - **Ca(HCO₃)₂** Calcium bicarbonate
 - **CaO** Calcium oxide
 - **CaSO₄ · ½2H₂O**
 - **CaSO₄·2H₂O** Gypsum og calcium sulphate hydrate
 - **CH₄** Methane
 - **CO** Carbon monoxide
 - **CO₂** Carbon dioxide
 - **Fe** Iron
 - **Fe-20B** Ferroboron alloy containing 20 wt% boron and iron making up the rest
 - **Fe-22Si-23Al** Alloy containing 22 wt% Si, 23wt% Al, and iron making up the rest
 - **Fe-24Si-11B** Alloy containing 24 wt% silicon, 11 wt% boron, and iron making up the rest
 - **Fe-41Si** Alloy containing 41 wt% Si and iron making up the rest
 - **Fe-75Si** Ferrosilicon containing 75 wt% silicon
 - **FeB** Ferroboron
 - **FeSi** Ferrosilicon
 - **FeSiAl** Alloy containing iron, silicon, and aluminium
 - **FeSiB** Alloy containing iron, silicon, and boron
 - **H₂SO₄** Sulphuric acid
 - **H₂O** Water
-

-
- **H₃BO₃** Boric acid
 - **Hg** Mercury
 - **KCl** Potassium chloride
 - **Mg** Magnesium
 - **MgO** Magnesium oxide
 - **NaCl** Sodium chloride
 - **NO_x**
 - **O** Oxygen
 - **PAH** Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbon
 - **S** Sulphur
 - **Si** Silicon
 - **SiB** Alloy containing silicon and boron
 - **SiC** Silicon carbide
 - **SiO₂** Silicon oxide, also known as silica
 - **SiO_x** Silicon oxides

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Chapter 1

Introduction

The demand for energy storage increases with the demand for renewable energy. Especially the variable energy sources, such as solar and wind power, requires energy storage. The periods of high energy production and energy consumption do not align, resulting in loss of energy without energy storage. To be able to utilise this energy, cheap and sustainable storage solutions are necessary [1, 2].

Figure 1.1: Illustration of the technology for the thermal energy storage. Renewable energy from wind and solar power charges the thermal energy storage, which can then supply heat or electricity [3].

THERMOBAT has proposed the use of the eutectic metal alloy Fe-24Si-11B as a phase change material (PCM) for thermal energy storage (TES). This works by storing energy as heat in a phase change from solid to liquid, further explained in Section 2.1. The Norwegian University of Science and Technology (NTNU) is responsible for investigating the production process and properties of this metal alloy, which is one of the components in the storage system. The goal is to produce the material from a mix of virgin and recycled or scrap material and have as low an environmental impact as possible. [2]

To assess the environmental impacts of the Fe-24Si-11B production, a life cycle assessment (LCA) was done in this study. LCA is a method of evaluating the environmental impacts of a process, product, or service. Multiple impact assessment methods can be used and CML-IA baseline, ReCiPE 2016 Endpoint (H), and IPCC 2021 GWP were used in this thesis.

Three different production routes were created for the production of Fe-24Si-11B; First, using colemanite and Fe-41Si which will be called the FeSi route. Second, using Fe-20B, iron (Fe), and silicon (Si), which will be called the FeB route. Finally, using colemanite and Fe-22Si-23Al, which will be called the FeSiAl route.

The goal is to evaluate which of these routes will have the lowest environmental impact and highlight which parts of the production has the highest impacts. Norway and Spain are two of the countries in this partnership, and likely places for the production of the alloy to take place. Therefore, a comparison of production taking place in Norway or Spain was conducted. Additionally, possible ways of reducing the environmental impact will be suggested.

Chapter 2

Theory

2.1 Thermal energy storage

Thermal energy storage is based on the principle of using energy to cool, heat, melt, solidify or vaporise a material, and retrieve this energy as heat when reversing the process. There are two main categories for TES: Sensible heat thermal energy storage (SHTES) and latent heat thermal energy storage (LHTES) [4].

2.1.1 Sensible heat thermal energy storage

SHTES is based on storing thermal energy through increasing the temperature of a solid or liquid, utilising the materials change in heat capacity and temperature during charging and discharging. The amount of heat stored can be given as a function, Equation 2.1, of the specific heat of the material, the temperature change and the mass of the material.

$$Q = \int_{T_i}^{T_f} mC_p dT = mC_{ap}(T_f - T_i) \quad (2.1)$$

where Q is the quantity of heat stored, T_i and T_f are the initial and final temperature respectively, m is the mass of the material, C_p is the specific heat, and C_{ap} is the average specific heat between T_i and T_f . Heat will be reduced through radiation, conduction and convection by both the storage material and through the reduced temperature due to cloudy weather or cooler nights. An example of this kind of system is a space heating systems using tanks of warm water as TES. [4]

2.1.2 Latent heat thermal energy storage

LHTES is based on a material absorbing and releasing heat to undergo a phase change, typically a solid-liquid phase change. Solid-gas and liquid-gas changes are

impractical due to the large volume change. Solid-solid and liquid-liquid changes have small volume change, but have a smaller heat capacity than a solid-liquid change. The material used for this kind of energy storage is called a PCM, and the storage capacity is given by Equation 2.2 below:

$$Q = \int_{T_i}^{T_m} mC_p dT + ma_m\Delta H_m + \int_{T_m}^{T_f} \quad (2.2)$$

where Q is the quantity of heat stored, T_i , T_m and T_f are the initial, melting and final temperature respectively, m is the mass of the material, C_p is the heat capacity, a_m is the fraction melted, and ΔH_m is the heat of melting per unit mass. LHTES have higher storage density in a narrower temperature range due to the high heat capacity at the phase transition. [4]

2.2 Phase change Materials

PCMs can store and release energy as both sensible and latent heat, where latent heat has the highest density. There are multiple criteria to the properties of the material to achieve the best PCM possible, which are as follows [4]:

Thermal properties:

- Melting temperature in operating range
- High phase transition latent heat per unit volume
- High heat capacity to provide extra storage through sensible heat
- High thermal conductivity of both phases

Physical properties:

- Small volume change under phase transition
- Low vapour pressure at operating temperature
- Favourable phase equilibrium
- Congruent melting of the PCM
- High density

Kinetic properties:

- No super-cooling
- High nucleation rate

-
- Adequate rate of crystallisation

Chemical properties:

- Long term chemical stability
- A completely reversible cycle
- Compatibility with the construction materials
- No corrosion influence on the construction material
- Non-toxic, non-flammable and non-explosive for safety

Most materials are unable to meet all the criteria, but progress in design and characterisation of new materials are opening for new possibilities [4]. Khare et al. [5] found that aluminium (Al), magnesium (Mg), and silicon carbide (SiC) were useful for TES in the range 400-700 °C. Gilpin [6] tried using pure silicon for ultra-high temperature energy storage. However, as silicon has a thermal expansion of 10%, breakage of the crucible is likely during solidification. Datas et al. [7] proposed a SiB alloy. Homa et al. [8] found that this alloy had strong penetration in a graphite crucible. An FeSiB alloy was suggested as a possible PCM material for the AMADEUS project due to its high latent heat, thermal conductivity, moderate melting point, and low cost. [1]

2.2.1 Fe-Si-B alloy

In a study by Jianmeng Jiao et al. [1] the eutectic FeSiB alloy was studied. This alloy was found to consist of 64.27 wt% Fe, 26.38 wt% Si, and 9.35 wt% boron (B) and has high latent heat at the melting temperature 1157 °C. The experiments were done in an isotropic graphite crucible. The isotropic structure and properties makes it easy to machine, and the covalent bonds make the crucible electrically conductive. The crucible is able to withstand long term use at temperatures above 2000 °C, and is chemically stable with some exceptions. The low thermal expansion and high thermal conductivity give a good shock resistance. The materials were tested using 1 to 4 thermal cycles of 1157 ± 20 °C and 1157 ± 100 °C.

The study found that the fusion enthalpy of eutectic FeSiB was 1250 kWh/m³, higher than most other PCM candidates. SiC and boron carbide (B₄C) were found at the edge of the treated alloy in the crucible. The alloy penetrated the crucible, however these materials act as a shield against further penetration. The penetration is therefore negligible and there were no degradation effects on the container. A shrinkage was found in the alloy, causing porosity. However, the lack of expansion is positive for the use as a PCM. [1]

2.3 Mass balance

The majority of masses are based on stoichiometric mass balances. These are calculated using Equation 2.3,

$$n = \frac{m}{M} \quad (2.3)$$

where n is the number of moles, m is the mass in g, and M is the molar mass of the element or compound in g/mol.

2.4 Thermochemistry and metallurgy

When the reductant metal has a greater affinity for the non-metal element than the desired metal, it is possible to do a metallothermic reduction. The non-metal element can be a halogen, sulphur (S), or oxygen (O). Oxygen is the case in this study.

How easily the metal oxide is reduced depends on the difference in oxygen affinity of the metal and the reductant. The oxygen affinity is indicated by its heat of formation. For comparison, the heat of formation can be expressed as ΔH per mol oxygen (kJ/mol O). The Gibbs free energy of formation, ΔG can give a quantitative measure for the stability of an oxide. The more negative the energy of formation at a given temperature, the greater reducing ability the metal will have for an oxide of less negative free energy. ΔG is related to ΔH by the following equation

$$\Delta G_T^\circ = \Delta H - T\Delta S \quad (2.4)$$

where T is the temperature and ΔS is the entropy and is always positive or 0 as it corresponds with the atomic disorder of the system with temperature. It should be noted that this gives a rough guide, and not a definitive answer.

Sufficient heat must be provided to drive the reaction as far to the right side of the equation as possible. Additionally enough heat to produce temperatures sufficient for separation of metal and slag, as well as heat losses, must be provided. Only the minimum required heat must be added to the reactions, because of the cost of heat and any excess heat added to exothermic reactions will result in moving the equilibrium to the left.

It is more difficult to find the heat of formation for slags, as they can be complex. The heat loss will vary with the size of charge and cannot be foretold. Establishing losses and compensating for this is done by trial and error. The chemical composition of ores can be used as a guide to improve the heat balance. Higher heat of reaction with aluminium or silicon will generally occur when the state of the oxide in the ore is higher. [9]

2.4.1 Auxiliary reactions

Several reactions require additional heat to fully produce liquid metal and slag. An addition of iron oxide and reactant can give a higher average heat of reaction. Additionally lower melting points are achieved. Aluminium can be added to increase the exothermicity of silicothermic reactions, as the products have high melting points. [9]

2.5 Boron

Boron is the element of atomic number 5 and belongs to group III in the periodic system. The melting point of B is 2074 °C. The element is used for microalloying steel and alloys to improve mechanical properties, mainly hardenability. Boron can be found in multiple minerals, e.g. colemanite and borax. Boron is typically an oxide, of which boron oxide (B_2O_3) is the most stable [10, 11].

2.5.1 Boron mining

Turkey has the largest boron reserves of 1 200 million tons and is the largest producer with 1.7 million tons in 2022 [12]. The mineral processing of boron can be divided into three stages: mining, mineral processing, and refining.

A layer covering the boron ore is removed using drilling-blasting methods. Then, excavators and loaders extract the ore. Rocks loosened by the drilling and blasted is excavated by hydraulic crawler excavators. These excavators are also used to load trucks for transportation. Ore is transported to stockpiles, where it can be fed to concentrator facilities as necessary.

An enrichment process takes place in the concentrator facilities. There are generally five steps: crushing, milling, screening, washing, and sieving. Clays that precipitate with the boron form the waste during the enrichment process. The mineral is then usually refined to boric acid (H_3BO_3), borax hydrates, or other boron compounds [13]. However, the mineral can also be used as it is after this stage. Processes and equipments are given in Table 2.1 below.

Table 2.1: Input, machines and devices, processes and outputs for both the open-pit mining and the enrichment process for boron [13].

Open-pit mining			
Inputs	Machines & devices	Processes	Outputs
Diesel fuel	Driller	Exploration	Air Emissions
Explosives	Hydraulic crawler excavator	Drilling	Waste emissions
Energy	Loader	Blasting	Overburden
Oil	Greyder	Excavation run-of-ore	
	Dozer	Loading	
		Transporting	
Enrichment process			
Inputs	Machines & devices	Processes	Outputs
Electricity	Apron feeder	Crushing	Rock waste
Water	Classifier screw	Milling	Water waste
Energy	Jaw crusher	Screening	Tailing
Oil	Roll crusher	Washing	Air emissions
	Belt conveyors	Sieving	
	Washer		

Turkbay et al. [13] has made a literature review collecting and translating papers about the Boron mining industry in Turkey, as these papers typically are written in Turkish. Some of the inputs for the mining pit and concentrator plant are given in Tables 2.2 and 2.3. However, outputs are not given in the paper.

Table 2.2: Inputs for open pit boron mine [13].

Facility	Dynamite	T.A.N.	Electric Capsule	Diesel Fuel	Oil	Electricity	Energy
	(kg/ton)	(kg/ton)	(piece/ton)	(l/ton)	(kg/ton)	(kWh/ton)	(kWh/ton)
Emet Hisarcık	0.002	0.033	0.001	0.336	0.015	-	0.373
Emet Espey	0.002	0.057	0.003	0.58	0.033	-	0.724
Bigadiç	0.0023	0.0461	0.0043	0.4141	0.0239	-	1.0081
Kırka	0.076	0.003	0.002	0.508	0.019	0.296	-
				(kg/ton)			
Kestelek	0.001	0.015	0.002	2.651	0.099	-	26.438

Table 2.3: Inputs for colemanite concentrator plant [13].

Facility	Gasoline (kg/ton)	Diesel (l/ton)	Oil (kg/ton)	Electricity (kWh/ton)	Energy (kWh/ton)
Emet Hisarcık	-	0.627	0.061	-	5.994
Emet Espey	-	0.827	0.061	-	9.045
Bigadiç	-	0	0.003	7.375	-
Kırka	0.0036	0.094 (kg/ton)	0.0277	11.1995	-
Kestelek	-	-	-	-	-

2.5.2 Boric acid production using sulphuric acid

Colemanite ($\text{Ca}_2\text{B}_6\text{O}_5 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$) contains several other minerals than boron oxide. Some of these are removed through the mineral processing and enrichment, however some are still left behind in the concentrated ore. One way of getting a higher purity of boron oxide is to create boric acid, which can be used as a raw material in ferroboration production [14] or for producing boron oxide. In Europe, boric acid is mainly produced from colemanite ore. The production occurs through Reaction 2.5 [15].

Reaction of colemanite with sulphuric acid (H_2SO_4) lead to formation of gypsum ($\text{CaSO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$). The gypsum is removed by filtration and boric acid can be crystallised by cooling the filtrated solution. Calcium sulphate hemihydrate ($\text{CaSO}_4 \cdot \frac{1}{2}\text{H}_2\text{O}$) can form at higher temperature. However, gypsum is advantageous as it removes more of the water during the process, resulting in a higher yield and purity of the process. The process should take place below the transition temperature between gypsum and calcium sulphate hemihydrate, but high enough to keep a high boric acid concentration. Commercially, the temperature is kept at 88-92 °C [15].

Some values for inputs for boric acid production can be found in the paper by Turkbay et al. [13], again with no outputs. The data is listen in Table 2.4 below. It can be seen that the process uses colemanite and sulphuric acid as in the process described.

Table 2.4: Inputs for refining colemanite to 1 ton boric acid [13].

Input	Unit	Amount
Colemanite	ton	1.5
Sulfuric acid	ton	0.9
Electricity	kWh	130
Steam	ton	1
Water	ton	25
Compressed air	m ³	15

2.5.3 Boric acid production using CO₂-sequestration

A paper by Gönen et al. [16] suggests a new method using CO₂-sequestration, which can be used for carbon dioxide (CO₂) storage. Carbon dioxide is dissolved in water and forms carbonic acid according to Reaction 2.6. This acid can then be utilised for acid leaching of colemanite, forming boric acid, Reaction 2.7. The calcium (CA) and carbonate ions can react to produce calcium carbonate (CaCO₃), Reaction 2.8. Bicarbonate ions can also form in the reaction, in which case calcium bicarbonate (Ca(HCO₃)₂) will be produced, Reaction 2.9.

2.6 Ferroboron

Reduction of B can be done using silicon, carbon (C), or aluminium. To create ferroboron, the presence of iron is added to the process.

The reaction for reduction by Si is given in Equation 2.10 below [11]. According to Oleg Polyakov [10], Si is not used in practice as the alloy does not exceed 4% B due to being thermodynamically unfavourable.

B₂O₃ can react with C to create pure B by the reaction below.

However, thermodynamically B₄C is more stable

Reduction through aluminium is the main choice when carbon content should be minimised [10]. The reaction is given in Equation 2.13

Figure 2.1: Ellingham diagram showing the Gibbs free energy for oxidation of the relevant elements for boron reduction.

2.6.1 Aluminothermic method

Ferroboron can be produced in a batch-wise process using aluminium powder to reduce boron and iron oxides. Only a small amount of energy is necessary to start the self-propagating reaction, as the aluminothermic co-reduction of boron and iron oxides is highly exothermic. Additionally, some magnesium can be added to the mix. At temperatures below the boiling point of magnesium, magnesium is the stronger reducing agent. Aluminium, on the other hand, is a stronger reducing agent above the boiling point of magnesium, where the metallothermic reactions generally take place [9].

The compounds are thoroughly mixed and charged into a refractory-lined pot and ignited, either top firing where the whole mix is ignited, or by igniting a starting mix where the rest of the charge is added as the reaction proceeds [9]. Electric furnace is the most widely used method for the aluminothermic method. It is also possible to

do the melting using a tilting furnace. A heated furnace melting bath can then be used for the next melting, reducing the consumption of refractories and the melting cycle. The melting can be divided into 3 periods: [11]

1. The formation of a melt
2. The reduction of oxides
3. The processing of slag by precipitant

Borate ore and secondary aluminium chips constitutes the main part of the charge. Iron-termite mix is made up of secondary iron oxides and aluminium chips, while the ignition mix consists of calcined borate ore, iron oxides and aluminium. The ignition mix constitutes approximately 6-7 % of the total charge, while the iron-termite mixture is 20-27 %, depending on the ferroboration grade, of the total charge.

The ignition mix is loaded and heated using an electric arc. When this mix has reacted and melted, half of the main charge is loaded and melted. Half of the iron-rich precipitant is then added and the furnace is turned of to tap the slag. The second halves of the main charge and precipitant mixture are then added. The temperature of the melt is supported at 1750 °C to 1780 °C. The rest of the slag is tapped, leaving the metal to cool down in the hearth. Smelting ferroboration (FeB) can also be done with both slag and alloy tapping. Better utilisation of latent and accumulated heat and reduced consumption of refractories can then be achieved. Details of the charge composition and the material balance can be found in Tables 2.5 and 2.6, respectively. [10]

Table 2.5: Composition of the charge for ferroboration smelting with aluminium reduction (wt%) [10].

Component of the Charge	Ignition	Main	Iron-Rich Precipitant
Borate ore	11.6	81.9	13.3
Iron oxide	58.1	-	64
Aluminum powder	18.6	18.1	22.7
Iron chips	11.6	-	-

Table 2.6: Material balance for smelting FeB using aluminothermic reduction of boric anhydride [10].

Input	kg	Output	kg
Boric anhydride (93 % B ₂ O ₃)	1200	FeB (21.8 % B)	1095
Iron ore (90 % Fe ₂ O ₃)	1400	Tapped slag (9.4 % B ₂ O ₃)	1200
Aluminium (99.2 % Al)	1167	Furnace slag (10.6 % B ₂ O ₃)	1858
Lime (88 % CaO)	340	Bottom slag (12.7 % B ₂ O ₃)	167
Magnesite bricks use	265	Dust in gas ducts (28 % B ₂ O ₃)	30
Total	4372	Total	4350

2.7 Aluminium

2.7.1 Primary aluminium production

Primary aluminum is produced by alumina (Al_2O_3), retrieved from the mineral bauxite. Bauxite is typically composed of hydrated aluminium oxides, hydrated aluminosilicates, iron oxides, hydrated iron oxides, titanium oxides, and silica (SiO_2) [17]. Bauxite can be found in several countries, but the largest reservoirs are in Guinea, Vietnam, and Australia in decreasing order. Despite Guinea having the largest reservoir with 7 400 million tons Bauxite, Australia has the largest bauxite production with 100 million tons in 2022. China, on the other hand, has the largest alumina production with 76 million tons in 2022 [18].

The aluminium productions consists of 4 main steps: bauxite mining, alumina refining, aluminium smelting and aluminium ingot casting [19]. Bauxite is usually found close to the surface, 1 to 2 m below the surface. The following are the typical steps when mining surface deposits [17, 20]:

- Using scrapers and bulldozers to clear vegetation and collect valuable topsoil.
- Remove overburden (material above the deposit).
- Blasting or ripping when ore parts are difficult to dig. This can be explosives, drilling or ripping with large bulldozers.
- Loading trucks which delivers to crushing facilities. The trucks range in size from 30 to 180 tons.
- Landscaping and rehabilitating back of the land.
- Crushing and sorting.
- Washing and further treatment for concentrating the ore if necessary.
- Delivery to refineries.

The bauxite ore is further refined to recover alumina for the aluminium production. This is typically done by the Bayer refining process, discovered by Karl Josef Bayer in 1888. The process consists of the four following stages [20]:

Digestion: Finely ground bauxite is fed into a digester, a steam-heated unit. Under pressure it is mixed with a hot solution of caustic soda. The aluminium oxide reacts with the solution and forms a new solution of sodium aluminate and a precipitate of sodium aluminium silicate.

Clarification: The sodium aluminate solution is separated from iron oxides and silica waste through three steps: first, the sand waste is removed and washed to recover caustic soda; second, red mud is separated from the solution; lastly, the sodium aluminate is filtered to remove remaining impurities.

Precipitation: The sodium aluminate is mixed with small amounts of fine alumina crystals in a tall precipitator vessel. When the solution is cooled, alumina hydrate has crystallised and is transported to the next stage. The remaining solution of caustic soda and some alumina is returned to the digesters.

Calcination: The alumina hydrate is washed and dried to remove any remaining solution. It is then heated to 1000 °C to remove water from the crystallisation, leaving alumina as a white, sandy material.

The achieved alumina is then processed into aluminium, commercially done using the Hall-Héroult smelting process. In this process, aluminium and oxygen are separated through electrolysis. This is done by passing an electric current through a molten alumina solution in the presence of carbon. Carbon is the lining at the bottom of pots or reduction cells, and these are connected to an electrical series called potline. Additionally, carbon is inserted at the top of the pot as carbon anodes, with the bottom of the anodes immersed in molten alumina solution.

The oxygen combine with the carbon from the anodes and form carbon dioxide gas, leaving molten aluminium at the bottom of the pot. Smelt is siphoned off and transferred to large holding furnaces. Removal of impurities and addition of alloying can be done, and the aluminium is then cast to ingots. [20]

China has the largest aluminium production in the world, with 40 million tons in 2022. However, as Norway also has a significant aluminium production, with 1.4 million tons in 2022, and is one of the countries in the THERMOBAT project, Norway is a likely source for the aluminium. [21]

2.7.2 Secondary aluminium production

Recycling aluminium scrap requires only 5 % of the energy necessary for primary aluminium production. The recycled aluminium is known as secondary aluminium. Aluminium can be recycled over and over without loss of mechanical properties [22]. Because aluminium produces an oxide layer that protects against corrosion, the metal experiences little degradation and mass loss. This means that it is possible to recover most of the aluminium in a product [23].

The secondary refinery industry is similar to the primary, but here aluminium scrap is the main input. After the aluminium products are scrapped, they can be returned to the metal flow in the production system. There are three main types of scrap, depending on where in the production system they occur: home scrap, new scrap, and old scrap.

Home scrap arises during melting and refining of aluminium, both primary and secondary. This scrap is never placed on the market and is recycled within the factory. New scrap is recovered from all stages in the manufacturing chain. Almost all of this scrap is recovered and recycled. Old scrap is recovered from end use products. This is usually of lower grade, as products can be worn out and affected

by the environment. There can also be different types of alloys mixed together. The old scrap is therefore typically sorted according to metal content and quality. [24]

Several types of wastes are generated in the recycling process. The amount depends on the quality and characteristics of the scrap and techniques used. Table 2.7 gives the wastes generated at the different stages of the production process and the environmental problems caused.

Table 2.7: Types of waste generated in secondary aluminium production processes and their environmental problems [25].

Stage	Type of waste	Environmental problem
Metallic treatment and separation of materials	Particles and dust	Atmospheric pollution
	Paint, rubber, plastics, and oils	Waste pollution
Preparation of loads	Particles	Atmospheric pollution
	Remains of raw materials	Waste pollution
Melting	Combustion gases (CO_x , NO_x) and particles	Atmospheric pollution
	Aluminium slags and saline slags	Waste pollution
Alloying	Aluminium slags	Waste pollution

The main wastes generated are saline slags, aluminium slags, and aluminium dust. Saline slags are a result from melting in a rotary furnace using saline fluxes. The composition of the saline slag will depend on the composition of the scrap and the composition and amount of salt used. Generally, the composition will be 3-5 % Al, 15-30 % Al_2O_3 , 30-55 % sodium chloride (NaCl), and 15-30 % potassium chloride (KCl). Approximately 1 ton of saline slag is generated for every ton of aluminium slag processed, and the saline slag is considered hazardous waste.

Aluminium slags results from melting in furnaces that don't use fluxes. The composition depend of the nature of the secondary raw materials. Aluminium materials from refineries, where scrap and slags are melted to produce ingots and billets, have a lower aluminium content and reduce the metallic yield of the slag. Aluminium materials from foundries, where the ingots and billets are melted and converted into parts and materials, have a higher aluminium content and thus increase the metallic yield.

Aluminium dust is retrieved from the suction system used in the factories. The dust is trapped in cyclones and sleeve filters and is a fine grain powder. The composition is complex, but generally consists of aluminium compounds, silicon, silicon oxides (SiO_x), metals, and various salts. The waste has a high reactivity, especially with humidity, and is therefore considered hazardous.

Aluminium slags are subject to shredding, milling and separation before they are recycled. Saline slags have high salt contents, and are therefore not recycled into metals. Instead, a process to recover the salts and recycle by-products have been created. The slag is milled and treated with water to dissolve the salts, producing a brine from which the salts can be recovered through recrystallisation. The insoluble fraction will contain aluminium oxide and aluminium particles. Depending on purity, this can be recovered and used in industry such as the cement industry. Gases created in the process can be recovered and used as fuel for the process. [25]

2.8 Silicon and ferrosilicon production

Submerged arc furnace (SAF) is the main process for silicon production. The primary raw material is quartz and reductants include coal, charcoal, wood chips and coke. Iron pellets are added to the process for ferrosilicon production. The materials are crushed and weighed before they are charged into the furnace. Carbon-based electrons are continuously consumed in the process. The overall carbothermic reduction is given by Reaction 2.14 below.

The silicon yield and amount of SiO gas is determined by the furnace operation and properties of the raw materials. This affects the composition of the off-gas. The silicon alloy produced is tapped and refined in a slag process before it is cast in moulds and cooled. The solid product can then be crushed to size and sent to customer.

Gas is mainly produced in the furnace, however, dust is created in almost every step of the production process. Most of the processes are equipped with ventilation systems and the off-gas is collected and filtered before it is released through a chimney. The furnace dust is commonly known as micro-silica and can be used in applications such as concrete filling. [26]

Table 2.8: Types of emissions and their place of origin in the silicon plant [26].

Type	Origin	Emission point
CO ₂ , CH ₄ and other GHG	Reductants, electrodes, carbon paste	SAF
NO _x	Combustion	SAF, tapping
SO ₂	Reductants	SAF
Dioxin	Reductants	SAF
PAH	Reductants, electrodes, carbon paste	SAF, tapping
Heavy metals	All raw materials	SAF, tapping, refining
Mechanically generated particles	Solid material handling	Conveyor belts, mills, sieves, etc.
Thermally generated particles	Liquid alloy in contact with air, SAF charge top	SAF, tapping, refining, casting

In a paper by Kero et al. [26] the emissions from silicon and ferrosilicon production were measured. The data for the carbon reductants are listed in Table 2.9 below.

Table 2.9: Typical composition of coal, coke, and electrode material used for Si and FeSi production and their calculated emission factors [26].

	Coke for FeSi	Coal for FeSi and Si	Electrode paste	Pre-baked electrodes
Fix C (wt%)	84	60	85	96
Volatile matter, VM (wt%)	9.5	38.5	9.5	0.7
% C in VM	80	65	70	80
% C total	91.6	85	91.7	96.6
CO ₂ emission factor (ton CO ₂ /ton reductant)	3.36	3.12	3.36	3.54

Reaction 2.14 shows that CO gas is created from the carbothermic reduction of silicon. This gas can then further oxidize to produce CO₂ gas, according to Reaction 2.15. Methane (CH₄) and volatile hydrocarbons can also be generated in the combustion of carbon materials and electrodes.

The CO₂ emission factor for silicon and common types of ferrosilicon in Norway can be seen in Table 2.10. The factor is given as ton CO₂ per ton metal, and it can be seen that the factor is 5.0 for metallurgical grade silicon (MG-Si) and 4.0 for ferrosilicon containing 75 wt% silicon (Fe-75Si).

Table 2.10: Generic CO₂ emission factors for Si and FeSi alloys (ton CO₂/ton tapped metal) [26].

Type of alloy	Generic emission factor
Ferrosilicon 45 % Si	2.5
Ferrosilicon 65 % Si	3.6
Ferrosilicon 75 % Si	4.0
Ferrosilicon 90 % Si	4.8
MG-Si (>98 % Si)	5.0

The study also covered the nitrogen oxides (NO_x) and SO_x concentrations in the off-gas. These values are given for Si and Fe-75Si production, and are listed in Table 2.11. The NO_x was found to be 22 kg per ton alloy and 15 kg per ton alloy for Si and Fe-75Si, respectively. For SO_x, the values are 13 kg per ton alloy and 24 kg per ton alloy, respectively, for Si and Fe-75Si. These are for the batch process, which is the traditional method and the assumed process for this study. [26]

Table 2.11: Averaged NO_x and SO_x concentrations in furnace off-gas, given as kg gas per ton product alloy [26].

Furnace type	Si furnace		FeSi-75 % furnace	
	Batch	Semi continuous	Batch	Semi continuous
NO _x (kg/ton)	22	11	15	7
SO _x (kg/ton)	13	11	24	21

Estimated distribution of heavy metals for a Si production plant are given in Table 2.12 below. The data to air is of most interest in this study, as these are the emissions. The emissions are 6 kg arsenic (As) and 0.10 kg mercury (Hg) per year for a plant producing 10 kilotons Si annually.

Table 2.12: Estimated distribution of heavy metals for a plant producing 10 kilotons silicon annually, all numbers given in kg per year [26].

	As	Cd	Cr	Cu	Hg	Pb	Zn
To air	6	0	0	0	0.10	0	0
In Si product	6	1	600	160	0.00	5	10
In microsilica	100	9	60	40	0.05	95	190
Total	112	10	660	200	0.15	100	200

C. Nøstvold [27] has done an LCA study with a comparison of Si production using bio based charge mixtures and commercial charge mixtures. The data used for the commercial charge mixes can be seen in Appendix A. The study is detailed, however when comparing with the values available in the paper by Kero et al. [26], some of the values are quite different. Both papers give a total CO₂ emission of approximately 5 ton per ton metal. However, Nøstvold calculated a value of 16.95

kg SO₂ per ton alloy for MIX95%. This is nearly 4 kg higher than the 13 kg SO₂ per ton alloy achieved by Kero et al. Nøstvold has a NO_x value twice as high as that of Kero et al. with 40.48 kg NO_x for MIX95%. The values for heavy metal also varies a lot compared to values given in the paper by Kero et al.

This is a good example of how LCA results can vary depending on the material available. Variations in impurities in the raw materials will vary, thus affecting the resulting emissions. If data is not available, calculations are made based on stoichiometric values from chemical equations, which typically results in over- and underestimations. As the values from Kero et al. are based on measurements and calculations from industry and the authors are professors at NTNU with experience in this field, values from this paper will be used forward.

Chapter 3

LCA Methodology

3.1 Life cycle assessment

Life cycle assessment, or life cycle analysis, is a measurement of the environmental impacts from the life cycle of a product, process, or service. The different parts of a life cycle, called life cycle stages, can have multiple impacts on the environment. LCA allows evaluation of a products total impact or the impact of the different stages. This can help make informed decisions regarding product development, marketing, strategic planning and policy making.

There are many types of LCA, and this will vary depending on the need. E.g. internal reports have less requirements than external. The methodology is standardised through a few different standards. In this report, the ISO 14040 and 14044 are used. There are four main phases to LCA, described by these standards: goal and scope, inventory analysis, impact assessment, and interpretation. Additionally, the method is iterative, illustrated in Figure 3.1. This means that continuously through the work, previous phases will be refined and revised depending on insight gained from the later phases. The four phases are described in the following sections. [28]

Figure 3.1: Illustration of the four phases from ISO 14040 and their iterative relations.

The LCA conducted in this thesis is done using SimaPro version 9.3.0.2 and the Ecoinvent 3 database.

3.1.1 Goal and scope

The goal and scope describes the how and why for the analysis, and ensures that the LCA is performed consistently. LCA gives a model of a complex reality, meaning multiple simplifications must be made. Carefully defining the scope and goal ensures that these simplifications do not influence and distort the results too much. The most important choices made in the study are described in the goal and scope [28]. The goal and scope should be defined with the commissioner and should be clearly defined and consistent with the intended application [29].

The goal should describe the intended application of the product, process, or service. The reasons for the study should also be described in this part, along with the intended audience and who the paper will be disclosed to. The scope describes the product system studied, meaning the functions of the system or systems in the case of comparative studies. This includes the functional unit, which describes the function of the system in line with the goal and scope. All inputs and outputs are considered in relation to and normalised to this unit. The scope also describes the system boundaries, which defines which describes what are taken into consideration and what is left out. This will depend on money, time, resources, and what is wanted by the commissioner. The allocation procedures describes how allocation of impacts are made when they are based on a choice. E.g. how much of the impact is given to the product and the by product. Methodology and impact categories based of impact assessment and interpretation must be described in the scope as well, along with the data requirements, assumptions, and limitations. [28, 29]

3.1.2 Inventory analysis

In the inventory analysis, the environmental inputs and outputs are studied. Environmental inputs is something taken out of the environment and added to the products life cycle. On the other hand, environmental outputs are taken from the products life cycle and added to the environment. These give the complete picture of the inventory [28]. The inventory analysis consists of four steps: preparing for data collection, data collection, calculation, and allocation. The reliability of the data is dependent on the reliability of the source and must be documented [30].

3.1.3 Impact assessment

In the impact assessment, conclusions are drawn to make better and more informed decisions. The environmental impacts collected and modelled in the inventory analysis are classified into categories [28]. This allows evaluation of the potential environmental impacts.

First the impact categories, category indicators and characterisation models are selected. It is important that the subjective choices made are documented. Then the inventory results are assigned to the impact categories, called classification. This is based on the impact assessment method chosen. Lastly, the calculation of category indicator results, called characterisation, is done. This is done by multiplying the inventory results with characterisation factors, typically done by a program. The calculation gives the contribution to the impact for each category indicator. The characterisation factors are provided by the assessment method.

There are two main types of impact categories, as they can be described on two different levels. There are the mid-point effects, which describes the effects on nature, e.g. acidification, global warming, ozone depletion, etc. The other category is end-point effects, which is the consequences of the mid-point effects. E.g. less biodiversity, shorter length of human life, and resource depletion. [31]

3.1.4 Interpretation

Interpretation is the last phase of the LCA. Here, the conclusions are checked to be well-substantiated. The ISO 14044 describes different tests to see if the data and procedures support the conclusions [28]. Accuracy and sensitivity should be discussed in this phase. Completeness can be controlled by evaluating whether all necessary data is complete and available. If not, justification and explanations must be made. In the interpretation, everything must be discussed in relation to the goal and scope to ensure the analysis is consistent.

3.2 Impact assessment methods

3.2.1 CML-IA baseline

The CML-IA baseline method, also known as CML 2001, was published by Center of Environmental Science of Leiden University (CML) in 2001. The guide describes the procedure for conducting LCA according to ISO standards. This includes an extensive list of substances and their impact categories, characterisation methods, and characterisation factors that are recommended. The guide aims to link the Ecoinvent data to the impact assessment factors for the problem oriented approach. This helps avoid discrepancies due to misunderstandings or different interpretations [32]. Impact categories, their units and short descriptions are given in Table 3.1 below.

Table 3.1: List of the CML-IA baseline impact categories, their units, and their description.

Impact category	Unit	Description
Abiotic depletion	kg Sb eq	Indicates the depletion of natural resources that are not fossil fuels
Abiotic depletion (fossil fuels)	MJ	Indicates the depletion of natural fossil fuel resources
Global warming potential (GWP100a or GWP)	kg CO ₂ eq	Indicates the potential global warming due to emission of greenhouse gases to air
Ozone layer depletion (ODP)	kg CFC-11 eq	Indicates the emission to air that causes the destruction of the ozone layer
Human toxicity	kg 1.4-DB eq	Indicates the impact of toxic substances to humans
Fresh water aquatic ecotox.	kg 1.4-DB eq	Impact of toxic substances to freshwater organisms
Marine aquatic ecotoxicity	kg 1.4-DB eq	Impact of toxic substances to marine organisms
Terrestrial ecotoxicity	kg 1.4-DB eq	Impact of toxic substances to terrestrial organisms
Photochemical oxidation	kg C ₂ H ₄ eq	Indicates the creation of smog by emissions of gases
Acidification	kg SO ₂	Indicates the acidification of soils and water due to gas emissions
Eutrophication	kg PO ₄ eq	Indicates the enrichment of ecosystems due to emission of nutritional elements

3.2.2 ReCiPe 2016 Endpoint (H)

The ReCiPe method is a method of combined midpoint and endpoint assessment method, with main contributors being RIVM, Radboud University, CML and Pré Sustainability [33]. This method calculate 18 midpoint indicators and three endpoint indicators [34]. Relations between the midpoint and endpoint indicators can be seen in Figure 3.2. In this LCA study, only the endpoint categories will be studied, as midpoint is given by the CML-IA method. The endpoint categories, their units and descriptions are given in Table 3.2 below.

Figure 3.2: Overview of the structure of the ReCiPe method, showing the relationship between midpoint and endpoint categories. Adapted from RIVM [34].

Table 3.2: List of ReCiPe endpoint impact categories, their units, and their description.

Impact category	Unit	Description
Damage to human health	Disability adjusted life years (DALY)	Damage to human health measured as lost years of life per person per year
Damage to ecosystems	species.yr	Damage to ecosystem diversity measured in species/year
Damage to resources	USD (2013)	Indicates the increased extraction cost of minerals and fossil fuels, measured in USD (2013)

3.2.3 IPCC 2021 GWP

The IPCC method was developed by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change. It contains the global warming potential (GWP) factor for different timeframes. In Simapro, the timeframes available are 20, 100, and 500 years. The GWP 100 is recommended as default, while GWP 20 is recommended for sensitivity analysis. The GWP 500 factors may also be used for sensitivity analysis according to SimaPro. [35]

Table 3.3: List of IPCC impact categories, their units, and their description.

Impact category	Unit	Description
GWP X - fossil	kg CO ₂ eq	The global warming potential due to fossil resources given for X number of years
GWP X - biogenic	kg CO ₂ eq	The global warming potential due to biogenic resources given for X number of years
GWP X - land transformation	kg CO ₂ eq	The global warming potential due to land transformation given for X number of years

Chapter 4

Inventory

The inventories for the unit processes are given in the following subsections. These give the input and output data added to the SimaPro software. The tables are given with Norway as the country for the general production. The inventory is equivalent for Spain, however, the electricity input has been changed to country mix for Spain. Whether a unit process takes place in Norway or Spain is clearly stated in the material names. This can be seen in the Results, Chapter 5.

All the three different production routes will produce slag. The treatment of the slags are not included in this LCA. Transportation has also not been included, as the main focus has been regarding the production processes themselves.

4.1 Production processes

4.1.1 FeSi route

The FeSi route is a production route for creating Fe-24Si-11B alloy using Fe-41Si and colemanite. Colemanite ore is obtained through mining, as described in Section 2.5.1. Because colemanite is a hydrate, water needs to be removed through calcination below 600 °C. Fe-75Si is produced using a carbothermic reduction of silica in the presence of iron, described in Section 2.8, which is then melted and mixed with iron at 1500 °C to create Fe-41Si. This alloy can then be mixed with the calcine colemanite to create the Fe-24Si-11B alloy. This process will also create a slag with composition $\text{CaO-26SiO}_2\text{-41B}_2\text{O}_3$. The slag will be considered a waste product. A flowchart of the process is given in Figure 4.1.

Figure 4.1: Flowchart of the production process of Fe-24Si-11B using colemanite and Fe-41Si, also called FeSi route.

4.1.2 FeB route

The FeB route is a production route for creating the Fe-24Si-11B alloy using FeB. Fe-20B is produced using aluminothermic reduction of iron ore and a B_2O_3 material, in this case anhydrous boric acid. This method is described in Section 2.6.1. The Fe-20B is then mixed with Fe and Si at 1600°C to create the Fe-24Si-11B alloy. This does not create a slag, however, slag is produced in the FeB production. This slag is considered a waste product of the process. A flowchart of the process is given in Figure 4.2.

Figure 4.2: Flowchart of the production process of Fe-24Si-11B using FeB, also called FeB route.

4.1.3 FeSiAl route

The FeSiAl route is a production route for creating the Fe-24Si-11B alloy using colemanite and a Fe-22Si-23Al alloy. The colemanite is mined according to the method in Section 2.5.1, and calcined below 600 °C to remove water. Fe-75Si, Al, and Fe are mixed at 1550 °C to produce the Fe-22Si-23Al alloy. This alloy is then melted with the calcined colemanite at 1650 °C to create the Fe-24Si-11B alloy. A slag with composition CaO-3SiO₂-54Al₂O₃-15B₂O₃ will also be produced, which will be considered a waste product. A flowchart of the process is given in Figure 4.3.

Figure 4.3: Flowchart of the production process of Fe-24Si-11B using colemanite and Fe-22Si-23Al, also called FeSiAl route.

4.2 FeSi route

Data for the mining process was gathered from paper by Turkbay et al. [13]. The data used is listed in Table 2.2. The mine Bigadiç was chosen as this mine has production of colemanite and ulexite. Additionally, the data for this mine was based on multiple papers. As the mine produces two different minerals, it is assumed that the data would be the same for mining of colemanite only. For Bigadiç there is no electricity output given and it is therefore assumed that the listed energy is electricity.

Dynamite and technical ammonium nitrate (T.A.N.) are not available in the Eco-invent database. As toxex is the only explosive available in the database, this has been used. To calculate the amount of toxex used, TNT-equivalence was used. Using the relative effectiveness, the estimated mass for an equivalent explosive can be calculated [36].

As no outputs were given in the paper by Turkbay et al. [13], the outputs from burning the fuels have been calculated using emission factors. Statistisk sentralbyrå (SSB) gives the CO_2 , SO_2 , and heavy metals emission factors for multiple fuels [37]. This was used to calculate the emissions for heavy fuel oil and diesel. To find the mass of diesel, density of 0.84 kg/l given by Miljødirektoratet was used [38]. The final inventory is listed in Table 4.1.

Table 4.1: Inventory data for mining of colemanite ore taking place in Turkey for the FeSi route.

Products and co-products		
Mined colemanite ore - FeSi route	kg	2.11
Inputs from nature		
Colemanite	kg	2.11
Materials and fuels		
Diesel {Europe without Switzerland} market for Cut-off, S	kg	$7.34 \cdot 10^{-4}$
Explosive, tovox {GLO} market for Cut-off, S	kg	$4.65 \cdot 10^{-5}$
Heavy fuel oil {Europe without Switzerland} market for Cut-off, S	kg	$5.05 \cdot 10^{-5}$
Electricity and heat		
Electricity, high voltage {TR} market for Cut-off, S	kWh	$2.13 \cdot 10^{-3}$
Emissions to air		
Arsenic	g	$3.96 \cdot 10^{-8}$
Cadmium	g	$1.24 \cdot 10^{-8}$
Carbon dioxide	g	2.49
Chromium	g	$1.05 \cdot 10^{-7}$
Copper	g	$1.27 \cdot 10^{-6}$
Lead	g	$1.24 \cdot 10^{-7}$
Mercury	g	$1.18 \cdot 10^{-8}$
Sulfur oxides	g	$9.12 \cdot 10^{-4}$

Similarly to the mining data, the data for the enrichment process of the colemanite ore was taken from the article by Turkbay et al. [13]. The emission outputs from the heavy fuel oil was calculated using the emission factors from SSB [37]. The final inventory is given in Table 4.2.

Table 4.2: Inventory data of the enrichment process of colemanite ore occurring at the concentrator plant in Turkey for the FeSi route.

Products and co-products		
Concentrated colemanite ore - FeSi route	kg	2.11
Materials and fuels		
Heavy fuel oil {Europe without Switzerland} market for Cut-off, S	kg	$6.33 \cdot 10^{-6}$
Mined colemanite ore - FeSi route	kg	2.11
Electricity and heat		
Electricity, high voltage {TR} market for Cut-off, S	kWh	0.0156
Emissions to air		
Arsenic	g	$3.61 \cdot 10^{-10}$
Carbon dioxide	g	0.0203
Cadmium	g	$6.33 \cdot 10^{-10}$
Chromium	g	$8.55 \cdot 10^{-9}$
Copper	g	$3.35 \cdot 10^{-9}$
Lead	g	$6.33 \cdot 10^{-9}$
Mercury	g	$1.27 \cdot 10^{-9}$
Sulfur dioxide	g	$1.13 \cdot 10^{-4}$

The inventory of calcination of the concentrated colemanite ore is based on mass balance from stoichiometric values. The electricity was calculated using the Heat & Material balance in HSC Chemistry. The materials were set to heat from room temperature to 600 °C.

Table 4.3: Inventory data of the calcination process for the FeSi route.

Products and co-products		
CaO-65B ₂ O ₃ - FeSi route	kg	1.65
Materials and fuels		
Concentrated colemanite ore - FeSi route	kg	2.11
Electricity and heat		
Electricity, high voltage {NO} market for Cut-off, S	kWh	1.38
Emissions to air		
Water	kg	0.465

The inputs for Fe-75Si production is calculated based on mass balance using stoichiometric values. Electricity is found using HSC Chemistry, heating the materials from room temperature to 2000 °C. The hard coal and coke is assumed to consist of

100 % carbon for simplicity. As SimaPro gives the amount of coke as energy rather than mass, the heating value 33.3 MJ/kg [39] was used. The outputs of the process was found using data from the paper by Kero et al. [26], which can be seen in Tables 2.10, 2.11, and 2.12 (Section 2.8). When using the numbers for heavy metals, 75 % of the emissions to air was used as the FeSi alloy contains 75 % silicon. This is a rough estimate. The full inventory is given in Table 4.4 below.

Table 4.4: Inventory data for production of Fe-75Si taking place in Norway for the FeSi route.

Products and co-products		
Fe-75Si - FeSi route - Norway	kg	0.603
Materials and fuels		
Coke {GLO} market for Cut-off, S	kWh	2.14
Hard coal {RoW} market for Cut-off, S	kg	0.542
Iron pellet {GLO} market for Cut-off, S	kg	0.151
Silica sand {GLO} market for Cut-off, S	kg	0.967
Electricity and heat		
Electricity, high voltage {NO} market for Cut-off, S	kWh	2.05
Emissions to air		
Arsenic	g	0.27
Carbon dioxide	kg	2.41
Lead	g	$4.50 \cdot 10^{-3}$
Nitrogen oxides	g	9.05
Sulfur oxides	g	14.5

The inventory of the Fe-41Si production (Table 4.5) was based on mass balance using stoichiometric values. The electricity was found using HSC Chemistry heating the materials from room temperature to 1500 °C.

Table 4.5: Inventory data for production of Fe-41Si.

Products and co-products		
Fe-41Si - Norway	kg	1.102
Materials and fuels		
Iron pellet {GLO} market for Cut-off, S	kg	0.499
Fe-75Si - Norway	kg	0.603
Electricity and heat		
Electricity, high voltage {NO} market for Cut-off, S	kWh	0.624

The inventory for production of 1 kg Fe-24Si-11B is based on stoichiometric values

(Table 4.6). The electricity was found using HSC Chemistry. The materials were set to heat from room temperature to 1650 °C.

Table 4.6: Inventory data for the production of Fe-24Si-11B for the FeSi route.

Products and co-products		
Fe-24Si-11B - FeSi route - Norway	kg	1.00
Materials and fuels		
CaO-65B ₂ O ₃ - Norway - FeSi route	kg	151
Fe-41Si - FeSi route - Norway Cut-off, S	kg	1.10
Electricity and heat		
Electricity, high voltage {NO} market for Cut-off, S	kWh	1.87
Outputs to technosphere: Waste and emissions to treatment		
Slag	kg	1.74

4.3 FeB route

The inventory for the Fe-20B production (4.7) is based on the mass balance given in the book Boron Ferroalloys [10]. This mass balance can be seen in Table 2.6, Section 2.6.1. The amount of energy necessary for the process was not given. Because the aluminothermic continues on its own once the material is ignited, it is expected that the energy required for the process is only the heating to ignition temperature. However, this temperature is not given. Since the temperature of the melt is said to be supported at 1750 to 1780 degrees, 1750 degrees is used as this temperature. The electricity is then found using HSC heating the materials from room temperature to 1750 °C.

Because some materials are not in the database, some changes were made. Iron ore in the Ecoinvent database is given as Fe ore containing 63 % Fe, while the ore described in Table 2.6 is given as ore containing 90 % Fe₂O₃. These are the same materials described in different manners, meaning the mass will be the same. On the other hand, magnesite bricks are not available in the database. As they are made up of mostly magnesium oxide (MgO), this was used as a substitution. It was then assumed that the mass of MgO would be the same as for the magnesite bricks.

A second Fe-20B production method was made using Al scrap. It was not found in literature that Al scrap or recycled Al can be used for this process, however it will have a large effect on the environmental impacts. The method was created to see how much the impact will differ. The inventory will be the same as for using primary Al, except the primary Al will be changed to "Aluminium scrap, post-consumer {GLO}| aluminium scrap, post-consumer, Recycled Content cut-off | Cut-off, S".

Table 4.7: Inventory data for the production of Fe-20B.

Products and co-products		
Fe-20B - Primary Al - FeB route	kg	0.550
Materials and fuels		
Aluminium, primary, ingot {RoW} market for Cut-off,S	kg	0.586
Boric acid, anhydrous, powder {GLO} market for Cut-off, S	kg	0.603
Iron ore, crude ore, 63% Fe {GLO} market for iron ore, crude ore, 63% Fe Cut-off, S	kg	0.703
Lime, packed {Europe without Switzerland} market for lime, packed Cut-off, S	kg	0.171
Magnesium oxide {GLO} market for Cut-off, S	kg	0.133
Electricity and heat		
Electricity, high voltage {NO} market for Cut-off, S	kWh	1.64
Outputs to technosphere: Waste and emissions to treatment		
Dust in gas ducts from aluminothermic ferroboron production	kg	0.015
Slag waste form aluminothermic ferroboron production	kg	1.62

The inventory for the silicon was created using the same method as for the Fe-75Si inventory given in Section 4.2, using data for silicon instead of for FeSi. For the heavy metals, the full values of emissions to air were used.

Table 4.8: Inventory data for the production of Si taking plane in Norway.

Products and co-products		
Silicon produced in Norway	kg	0.240
Materials and fuels		
Coke {GLO} market for Cut-off, S	kWh	0.570
Hard coal {RoW} market for Cut-off, S	kg	0.144
Silica sand {GLO} market for Cut-off, S	kg	0.513
Electricity and heat		
Electricity, high voltage {NO} market for Cut-off, S	kWh	1.048
Emissions to air		
Arsenic	mg	0.144
Carbon dioxide	kg	1.2
Mercury	mg	$2.4 \cdot 10^{-3}$
Nitrogen oxides	g	5.28
Sulfur oxides	g	3.12

The inventory of the Fe-24Si-11B alloy is given in Table 4.9 below. The mass balance was found using stoichiometric values, while the electricity was found using HSC Chemistry. The materials were set to heat from room temperature to 1600 °C.

Table 4.9: Inventory data for the production of Fe-24Si-11B for the FeB route.

Products and co-products		
Fe-24Si-11B - FeB route - Spain	kg	1.00
Materials and fuels		
Fe-20B - FeB route - Spain	kg	0.550
Iron pellet {GLO} market for Cut-off, S	kg	0.210
Silicon produced in Norway	kg	0.240
Electricity and heat		
Electricity, high voltage {NO} market for Cut-off, S	kWh	0.709

4.4 FeSiAl route

The inventory for mining, enrichment, and calcination (Tables 4.10, 4.11, and 4.12) of colemanite were found using the same method as for the respective inventories in the FeSi route, Section 4.2.

Table 4.10: Inventory data for the mining of colemanite taking place in Turkey for the FeSiAl route.

Products and co-products		
Mined colemanite ore - FeSiAl route	kg	0.977
Inputs from nature		
Colemanite	kg	0.977
Materials and fuels		
Diesel {Europe without Switzerland} market for Cut-off, S	kg	$3.40 \cdot 10^{-4}$
Explosive, tovox {GLO} market for Cut-off, S	kg	$2.15 \cdot 10^{-5}$
Heavy fuel oil {Europe without Switzerland} market for Cut-off, S	kg	$2.34 \cdot 10^{-5}$
Electricity and heat		
Electricity, high voltage {TR} market for Cut-off, S	kWh	$9.85 \cdot 10^{-4}$
Emissions to air		
Arsenic	g	$1.83 \cdot 10^{-8}$
Cadmium	g	$5.74 \cdot 10^{-9}$
Carbon dioxide	g	1.87
Chromium	g	$4.86 \cdot 10^{-8}$
Copper	g	$5.90 \cdot 10^{-7}$
Lead	g	$5.74 \cdot 10^{-8}$
Mercury	g	$5.46 \cdot 10^{-9}$
Sulfur dioxide	g	$9.27 \cdot 10^{-6}$

Table 4.11: Inventory data for the enrichment process of colemanite taking place in Turkey for the FeSiAl route.

Products and co-products		
Concentrated colemanite ore - FeSi route	kg	2.11
Materials and fuels		
Heavy fuel oil {Europe without Switzerland} market for Cut-off, S	kg	$2.93 \cdot 10^{-6}$
Mined colemanite ore - FeSi route	kg	2.11
Electricity and heat		
Electricity, high voltage {TR} market for Cut-off, S	kWh	$7.21 \cdot 10^{-3}$
Emissions to air		
Arsenic	g	$1.67 \cdot 10^{-10}$
Carbon dioxide	g	$9.38 \cdot 10^{-3}$
Cadmium	g	$2.93 \cdot 10^{-10}$
Chromium	g	$3.96 \cdot 10^{-9}$
Copper	g	$1.55 \cdot 10^{-9}$
Lead	g	$2.93 \cdot 10^{-9}$
Mercury	g	$5.86 \cdot 10^{-10}$
Sulfur oxides	g	$5.23 \cdot 10^{-5}$

Table 4.12: Inventory for the calcination of colemanite for the FeSiAl process.

Products and co-products		
CaO-65B ₂ O ₃ - FeSiAl route	kg	0.762
Materials and fuels		
Concentrated colemanite ore - FeSiAl route	kg	0.977
Electricity and heat		
Electricity, high voltage {NO} market for Cut-off, S	kWh	0.424
Emissions to air		
Water	kg	0.215

The inventory for Fe-75Si for the FeSiAl route, Table 4.13, was found in the same manner as for Fe-75Si for the FeSi route, 4.2.

Table 4.13: Inventory for the production of Fe-75Si taking place in Norway for the FeSiAl route.

Products and co-products		
Fe-75Si - FeSiAl route - Norway	kg	0.347
Materials and fuels		
Coke {GLO} market for Cut-off, S	kWh	2.14
Hard coal {RoW} market for Cut-off, S	kg	0.542
Iron pellet {GLO} market for Cut-off, S	kg	0.151
Silica sand {GLO} market for Cut-off, S	kg	0.967
Electricity and heat		
Electricity, high voltage {NO} market for Cut-off, S	kWh	2.05
Emissions to air		
Arsenic	g	0.208
Carbon dioxide	kg	0.156
Mercury	g	$2.60 \cdot 10^{-3}$
Nitrogen oxides	g	5.21
Sulfur oxides	g	8.33

The inventory for Fe-22Si-23Al production was found using stoichiometric mass balance. To lower the environmental impact, recycled scrap aluminium was chosen from the Ecoinvent database. Note that this material has no impact as it is a scrap material and the production impact is allocated to the previous product. Electricity was calculated using HSC chemistry, heating the materials from room temperature to 1550 °C.

Table 4.14: Inventory for the production of Fe-22Si-23Al.

Products and co-products		
Fe-22Si-23Al - FeSiAl route - Norway	kg	1.18
Materials and fuels		
Aluminium scrap, new {GLO} aluminium scrap, new, Recycled Content cut-off Cut-off, S	kg	0.272
Fe-75Si - FeSiAl route	kg	0.347
Iron pellet {GLO} market for Cut-off, S	kg	0.563
Electricity and heat		
Electricity, high voltage {NO} market for Cut-off, S	kWh	0.503

Mass balance using stoichiometric values was used to find the inventory for the Fe-24Si-11B production. HSC chemistry was used to calculate the electricity heating the materials from room temperature to 1650 °C.

Table 4.15: Inventory for the production of Fe-24Si-11B for the FeSiAl route.

Products and co-products		
Fe-24Si-11B - FeSiAl route - Norway	kg	1.00
Materials and fuels		
CaO-65B2O3 - FeSiAl route - Norway	kg	0.762
Fe-22Si-23Al - FeSiAl route - Norway	kg	1.18
Electricity and heat		
Electricity, high voltage {NO} market for Cut-off, S	kWh	0.661
Waste and emissions to treatment		
CaO-2SiO2-54Al2O3-15B2O3 - FeSiAl route	kg	0.952

Chapter 5

Results

This chapter gives the results for the three different impact methods. First, an overall comparison will be given, then a more detailed overview for contribution will be given for the different impact categories. Note that for the FeB route, only the route using scrap Al will be shown in detail as this is the best case scenario for this route. Also note that when electricity in Spain is mentioned, this refers only to production routes with the main production is happening in Spain.

5.1 CML-IA baseline

This section gives the results from the CML-IA baseline method. The results are given in Table B.1, Appendix B. These are visualised in Figure 5.1. It can be seen that the FeB route using primary Al has the largest impact in all categories, except terrestrial ecotoxicity where FeSi route has the highest impact.

Figure 5.1: Results for the impact categories using the CML-IA baseline method when comparing the different production methods.

Figure 5.2 gives the comparison of the production routes in the different impact categories from the data given in Table B.1, but without FeB using primary Al. This allows for easier comparison of the other production routes.

Figure 5.2: Results for the impact categories using the CML-IA baseline method when comparing the different production methods excluding FeB using primary Al.

From the graph it can be seen that FeB route using scrap Al is still the route with highest impact in most categories. However, FeSi has a higher impact in abiotic depletion of fossil fuels, global warming potential, terrestrial ecotoxicity and eutrophication. FeSiAl has the lowest impact in all categories, except for terrestrial ecotoxicity where FeB using scrap Al has the lowest impact.

The following sections will give more details into each impact category. The distribution of the impacts within the categories are given for each of the production route, as well as the total impacts.

5.1.1 Abiotic depletion

Detailed values for the abiotic depletion contribution is given in Table B.2, using a cut-off of 1 %. The data is visualised in Figure 5.3. It can be seen that FeB has a much higher impact in this category, with $8.03 \cdot 10^{-5}$ and $8.09 \cdot 10^{-5}$ kg SB eq for Norway and Spain, respectively. These values are from boric acid, with a small amount from electricity in Spain. For FeSi the values for Norway and Spain are $1.61 \cdot 10^{-6}$ and $2.27 \cdot 10^{-6}$ kg SB eq, respectively, from iron pellets and electricity in Spain. Finally, FeSiAl has values $1.30 \cdot 10^{-6}$ and $1.71 \cdot 10^{-6}$ kg SB eq for Norway and Spain, respectively. These values are also caused by iron pellet and electricity in Spain.

Figure 5.3: Distribution of abiotic depletion of the different production routes. Data is given in Table B.2. A cut-off of 1 % was used and values are given in kg Sb eq.

5.1.2 Abiotic depletion (fossil fuels)

Figure 5.4 gives an overview of the detailed values for abiotic depletion of fossil fuels for the different production routes, given in Table B.3. Within each country mix, it can be seen that FeSi has the highest impact, while FeSiAl has the lowest. FeSi has an impact of 20.10 and 28.87 MJ for and FeSiAl has an impact of 7.57 and 13.02 MJ for Norway and Spain, respectively. The main contributions to both of these routes are coke, hard coal, and electricity in Spain. For the FeB route, the main contributions are boric acid, hard coal, and electricity in Spain. FeB has an impact of 15.40 and 23.47 MJ for Norway and Spain, respectively.

Figure 5.4: Distribution of abiotic depletion for fossil fuels of the different production routes. Data is given in Table B.2. A cut-off of 1 % was used and values are given in MJ.

5.1.3 Global warming potential (GWP100a)

Figure 5.5 gives the distribution of GWP based on Table B.4. FeSi has the highest and FeSiAl the lowest impact within each country mix. FeSi has an impact of 2.62 and 3.37 kg CO₂ respectively for Norway and Spain. FeSiAl has an impact 1.65 and 2.11 kg CO₂ eq for Norway and Spain. Both have the highest contribution from the Fe-75Si production, with electricity in Spain being the second largest contributor for the Spanish country mix. FeB has the highest contributions from boric acid, Si production, and electricity in Spain. The total impacts of FeB in Norway and Spain are 2.21 and 2.90 kg CO₂ eq.

Figure 5.5: Distribution of global warming potential of the different production routes. Data is given in Table B.4. A cut-off of 1 % was used and values are given in kg CO₂ eq.

5.1.4 Ozone layer depletion (ODP)

The distribution for ozone layer depletion is given in Figure 5.6, with the detailed results in Table B.5. Within each country mix, FeB production route has the highest impact, while FeSiAl has the lowest. FeSi and FeSiAl has their main contributions from coke, hard coal, and electricity in Spain. The total impacts for FeSi are $5.15 \cdot 10^{-8}$ and $9.15 \cdot 10^{-8}$ kg CFC-11 eq for Norway and Spain. FeSiAl has $2.23 \cdot 10^{-8}$ and $4.71 \cdot 10^{-8}$ as impacts for Norway and Spain, respectively. FeB has boric acid as main contributor. Electricity in Spain, coke and iron are the largest contributors following boric acid. The total impacts for FeB are $7.73 \cdot 10^{-8}$ and $1.14 \cdot 10^{-7}$ kg CFC-11 eq for Norway and Spain.

Figure 5.6: Distribution of ODP of the different production routes. Data is given in Table B.5. A cut-off of 1 % was used and values are given in kg CFC-11 eq.

5.1.5 Human toxicity

Details of the distribution for human toxicity is given in Table B.6, and visualised in Figure 5.7. FeB has the largest impact in this category, mostly from boric acid. Coke and electricity in Spain are the largest contributors following boric acid. The total impacts of FeB are 2.80 and 3.04 kg 1.4-DB eq, respectively, for Norway and Spain. The FeSiAl route has the lowest impact in human toxicity, with 0.38 and 0.54 kg 1.4-DB eq for Norway and Spain. Both FeSi and FeSiAl has coke, electricity in Spain and hard coal as their main contributors. FeSi has total impacts 0.84 and 1.10 for Norway and Spain.

Figure 5.7: Distribution of human toxicity of the different production routes. Data is given in Table B.6. A cut-off of 1 % was used and values are given in kg 1.4-DB eq.

5.1.6 Fresh water aquatic ecotoxicity

Figure 5.8 gives the distribution of fresh water aquatic ecotoxicity, based on the data in Table B.7. FeSiAl has the lowest impact in this category with 0.21 and 0.36 kg 1.4-DB eq for Norway and Spain, respectively, while FeB has the highest with 1.68 and 1.90 kg 1.4-DB eq. FeSi has impacts of 0.50 and 0.74 kg 1.4-DB eq for Norway and Spain. FeSi and FeSiAl have coke, electricity in Spain, and hard coal as their main contributors. For FeB, boric acid has the largest contribution, followed by the electricity in Spain.

Figure 5.8: Distribution of fresh water aquatic ecotoxicity of the different production routes. Data is given in Table B.7. A cut-off of 1 % was used and values are given in kg 1.4-DB eq.

5.1.7 Marine aquatic ecotoxicity

Detailed values for the marine aquatic ecotoxicity distribution can be found in Table B.8, and are visualised in Figure 5.9. Within each country mix, FeSiAl has the lowest impacts with 998.49 and 1728.76 kg 1.4-DB eq for Norway and Spain, respectively, and FeB the highest impacts with 2743.87 and 3824.10 kg 1.4-DB eq. FeSi has impacts of 1585.43 and 2758.16 kg 1.4-DB eq for Norway and Spain. Both FeSi and FeSiAl have their main contributions from coke, electricity in Spain, hard coal, and iron pellet. FeB has impact mainly from boric acid and electricity in Spain.

Figure 5.9: Distribution of marine aquatic ecotoxicity of the different production routes. Data is given in Table B.8. A cut-off of 1 % was used and values are given in kg 1.4-DB eq.

5.1.8 Terrestrial ecotoxicity

The distribution of terrestrial ecotoxicity is given in Figure 5.10, based on data in Table B.9. FeSi route has the highest impact with 0.11 kg 1.4-DB eq for both Norway and Spain, followed by FeSiAl with 0.074 kg 1.4-DB eq for both Norway and Spain. Both as a result from the Fe-75Si production. FeB has the lowest impact on terrestrial ecotoxicity, from boric acid. The impacts for Norway and Spain are 0.0032 and 0.0040 kg 1.4-DB eq, respectively.

Figure 5.10: Distribution of terrestrial ecotoxicity of the different production routes. Data is given in Table B.9. A cut-off of 1 % was used and values are given in kg 1.4-DB eq.

5.1.9 Photochemical oxidation

Table B.10 gives the detailed data of the distribution for photochemical oxidation. These are shown in Figure 5.11. FeB has the highest impact, within the country mixes, in this category with $5.19 \cdot 10^{-4}$ and $7.06 \cdot 10^{-4}$ kg C_2H_4 eq for Norway and Spain, respectively, while FeSiAl has the lowest with $1.27 \cdot 10^{-4}$ and $2.53 \cdot 10^{-4}$ kg C_2H_4 eq. FeSi has impacts of $3.18 \cdot 10^{-4}$ and $5.21 \cdot 10^{-4}$ kg C_2H_4 for Norway and Spain. The FeB route has boric acid, coke, and electricity in Spain as the main contributors. FeSi and FeSiAl have the main contributions from coke, electricity in Spain, and hard coal.

Figure 5.11: Distribution for photochemical oxidation of the different production routes. Data is given in Table B.10. A cut-off of 1 % was used and values are given in kg C_2H_4 eq.

5.1.10 Acidification

The detailed data of distribution for acidification is given in Table B.11 and visualised in Figure 5.12. Within each country mix, FeB route has the highest impacts with 0.015 and 0.020 kg SO_2 for Norway and Spain, respectively, while FeSiAl has the lowest impacts with $4.46 \cdot 10^{-3}$ and $7.95 \cdot 10^{-3}$ kg SO_2 eq. FeSi has impacts of $7.92 \cdot 10^{-3}$ and 0.014 kg SO_2 for Norway and Spain. FeB has boric acid, electricity in Spain, Fe ore, and silicon production as the largest contributors. For FeSi and FeSiAL, Fe-75Si, hard coal and electricity in Spain are the largest contributors.

Figure 5.12: Distribution of acidification of the different production routes. Data is given in Table B.11. A cut-off of 1 % was used and values are given in kg SO₂ eq.

5.1.11 Eutrophication

Figure 5.13 gives the distribution for eutrophication of the different production routes, based on data in Table B.12. Within each country mix, FeSi has the largest impacts with $3.83 \cdot 10^{-3}$ and $5.04 \cdot 10^{-3}$ kg PO₄ eq for Norway and Spain, respectively, while FeSiAl has the lowest impacts with $1.79 \cdot 10^{-3}$ and $2.54 \cdot 10^{-3}$ kg PO₄ eq. The total impacts of FeB are $3.50 \cdot 10^{-3}$ and $4.61 \cdot 10^{-3}$ kg PO₄ eq for Norway and Spain. For FeSi and FeSial, the main contributors are coke, electricity in Spain, Fe-75Si production, and hard coal. The main contributions for FeB are boric acid, electricity in Spain, hard coal, and silicon production.

Figure 5.13: Distribution of eutrophication of the different production routes. Data is given in Table B.12. A cut-off of 1 % was used and values are given in kg PO₄ eq.

5.2 ReCiPe 2016 Endpoint (H)

This section gives the results gathered from the ReCiPe endpoint method. The results are visualised in Figure 5.14, and more detailed results can be found in Table C.1 in Appendix C. It can be seen that the FeB route using primary Al has the highest impact in all categories.

Figure 5.14: Results for the endpoint impact categories using the ReCiPe endpoint method when comparing the different production methods.

A comparison of the different impact of the production routes excluding FeB route using primary Al is given in Figure 5.15, based on the data in Table C.1. This graph allows for easier comparison of the other production routes. Within each country mix, FeSi has the highest impact on human health and ecosystems, while FeB has the highest in resources. FeB has the lowest impact in human health, while FeSiAl has the lowest impact in both ecosystems and resources.

Figure 5.15: Results for the endpoint impact categories using the ReCiPe endpoint method when comparing the different production methods excluding FeB using primary Al.

The following sections will give more details into each impact category. The distributions within each category are given for each of the production routes, as well as the total impacts.

5.2.1 Human health

The distribution of human health impacts are given in Figure 5.16, based on data in Table C.2. Within each country mix, it can be seen that FeSi has the highest impacts with $1.36 \cdot 10^{-5}$ and $1.55 \cdot 10^{-5}$ DALY for Norway and Spain, while FeB has the lowest with $7.28 \cdot 10^{-6}$ and $9.09 \cdot 10^{-6}$. FeSiAl has impacts of $8.54 \cdot 10^{-6}$ and $9.76 \cdot 10^{-6}$ DALY for Norway and Spain. FeSi and FeSiAl have coke, electricity in Spain, Fe-75Si and hard coal as the largest contributors. The main contributions to the impact of FeB route are boric acid, electricity Spain, MgO, and Si production.

Figure 5.16: Distribution of human health impact of the different production routes. Data is given in Table C.2. A cut-off of 1 % was used and values are given in DALY.

5.2.2 Ecosystems

Figure 5.17 gives the distribution of ecosystem for the different production route. More detailed data is given in Table C.3. Within each country mix, FeSi has the highest impacts with $1.42 \cdot 10^{-8}$ and $1.79 \cdot 10^{-8}$ species.yr for Norway and Spain respectively, while FeSiAl has the lowest impacts with $8.64 \cdot 10^{-8}$ and $1.10 \cdot 10^{-8}$. FeB route has impacts of $1.26 \cdot 10^{-9}$ and $1.61 \cdot 10^{-8}$ species.yr for Norway and Spain. The main contributions to the impacts of FeSi and FeSiAl are coke, electricity in Spain, Fe-75Si production, and iron pellets. For FeB, the largest contributors are boric acid, electricity in Spain, and Si production.

Figure 5.17: Distribution of ecosystems impact of the different production routes. Data is given in Table C.3. A cut-off of 1 % was used and values are given in species.yr.

5.2.3 Resources

Detailed data for the distribution of impact on resources are given in Table C.4, and are visualised in Figure 5.18. Within each country mix, FeB has the highest impacts of 0.10 and 0.14 USD2013 for Norway and Spain respectively, while FeSiAl has the lowest impacts with 0.030 and 0.060 USD2013. FeSi has impacts of 0.059 and 0.11 USD2013 for Norway and Spain. The highest contributions to the impacts of FeB are boric acid, Electricity in Spain, hard coal, and silica sand. For FeSi and FeSiAl, the largest contributors are coke, electricity in Spain, hard coal, and iron pellet.

Figure 5.18: Distribution of resources of the different production routes. Data is given in Table C.4. A cut-off of 1 % was used and values are given in USD2013.

5.3 IPCC

This section gives the results from the IPCC method. The results for comparison are given in Table D.1, Appendix D. The data is visualised in Figure 5.19. It can be seen that FeB using primary Al has the highest impact in all categories, while the others are closer in impact.

Figure 5.19: Results for the impact categories using IPCC method when comparing the different production methods

Figure 5.20 gives the comparison for the different impact categories, but excludes the FeB route using primary Al. This allows for easier comparison of the other production routes. For GWP100 fossil, it can be seen that within the country mixes, FeSi has the highest impact and FeSiAl the lowest. For biogenic, FeB using scrap Al has the highest impact and FeSiAl the lowest. Finally, it can be seen that

within each country mix for land transformation, FeB using Al scrap has the highest impact, while FeSiAl has the lowest. Spain has a much larger impact in this category when compared to Norway.

Figure 5.20: Results for the impact categories using IPCC method when comparing the different production methods excluding FeB using primary Al.

The following sections gives a more detailed overview of each impact category. The distribution for each production route and the total impacts are given for each category.

5.3.1 GWP100 - fossil

Figure 5.21 gives the distribution of the fossil GWP, based on the data given in Table D.2. Within each country mix, FeSi route can be seen to have the highest impact with 2.63 and 3.37 kg CO₂ eq for Spain and Norway respectively, while FeSiAl has the lowest with 1.65 and 2.11 kg CO₂ eq. FeB has impacts of 2.22 and 2.89 kg CO₂ eq for Norway and Spain. The largest contribution to this is from boric acid, electricity in Spain, MgO, and Si production. For FeSi and FeSiAl, the main contributors are coke, electricity in Spain, Fe-75Si production, and hard coal.

Figure 5.21: Distribution of fossil GWP100 of the different production routes. Data is given in Table D.2. A cut-off of 1 % was used and values are given in kg CO₂ eq.

5.3.2 GWP 100 - biogenic

The distribution for the biogenic GWP is given in Figure 5.22, with more detailed data given in Table D.3. FeB route has the highest impact with $4.74 \cdot 10^{-3}$ and $5.01 \cdot 10^{-3}$ kg CO₂ eq in Norway and Spain, with boric acid, electricity in Spain, electricity in Norway, and lime as the largest contributions. FeSiAl has the lowest impacts with $1.44 \cdot 10^{-3}$ and $1.63 \cdot 10^{-3}$ kg CO₂ eq for Norway and Spain respectively, while FeSi has impacts of $2.13 \cdot 10^{-3}$ and $2.43 \cdot 10^{-3}$.

Figure 5.22: Distribution of biogenic GWP100 of the different production routes. Data is given in Table D.3. A cut-off of 1 % was used and values are given in kg CO₂ eq.

5.3.3 GWP 100 - land transformation

Detailed data of the distribution for land transformation GWP is given in Table D.4 and are visualised in Figure 5.23. Within each country mix, FeB has the highest impacts with $2.06 \cdot 10^{-3}$ and $7.66 \cdot 10^{-3}$ kg CO₂ eq for Norway and Spain respectively, while FeSiAl has the lowest impacts with $9.20 \cdot 10^{-4}$ and $4.70 \cdot 10^{-3}$. FeSi has impacts of $1.33 \cdot 10^{-3}$ and $7.40 \cdot 10^{-3}$ kg CO₂ eq. For FeSi and FeSiAl the main contributors are electricity in Spain, electricity in Norway, and silica sand. The main contributions for FeB are boric acid, electricity in Spain, electricity in Norway, and silica sand.

Figure 5.23: Distribution of land transformation GWP100 of the different production routes. Data is given in Table D.4. A cut-off of 1 % was used and values are given in kg CO₂ eq.

Chapter 6

Interpretation

The FeB route using primary Al has the highest impact in most of the impact categories. Primary Al production is highly energy intensive and carbon is used as the reduction material, resulting in high emissions. Because of this, this route was not considered in detail. A route using scrap Al instead of primary Al for the Fe-20B production was considered. However, there is no information available about the possibility of using scrap Al or recycled Al, meaning this scenario is hypothetical.

As scrap aluminium is considered without impact, the impact being allocated to the previous lifetime, this considerably reduces the impact of the process. This scenario still had a higher impact in most of the impact categories, however it was more comparable to that of FeSi and FeSiAl.

It was found that boric acid was one of the largest contributors in most of the impact categories for the FeB route. As boric acid was taken from the Ecoinvent database, it will have more detailed information of impacts from mining of resources and production processes to achieve this material. This means there will be more values to add up to the impact, compared to a less detailed inventory. Anhydrous boric acid is one of the more common materials for producing Fe-20B. Potentially, colemanite could be used directly. However, this process has a lower boron yield and it is difficult to reach 20 % B in the alloy, and would result in needing a larger amount of colemanite. It is unknown how this would compare with boric acid on the environmental impacts.

Another process that had larger contributions to the impacts of the FeB route were Si production. The impacts of Si production are high due to the use of carbothermic reduction. Much of this impact can be reduced by changing the fossil fuels to biofuels, such as charcoal and wood chips. Although the same amount of carbon will be needed and CO₂ emissions will be similar, the impact will be lowered. This is because plants remove CO₂ from the atmosphere during their lifetime, which is also considered and reduces the total impact. This is something currently under research in the industry. CO₂ capture and energy recovery are other methods to reduce the impact and utilise the process better, which is used in the industry but was not considered in this study.

All of this will also apply to the production of Fe-75Si, which was the largest contributor to the impacts of the FeSi and FeSiAl routes in many of the categories. The raw materials used for the process, such as coke and hard coal, also had a larger contribution to these production routes compared to FeB. The fossil raw materials could be replaced with the biofuels, reducing the impact from these as previously mentioned.

Replacing virgin materials with recycled or scrap materials when possible will have large impacts on the reduction of impact, as could be seen with the FeB route. If possible, it would therefore be beneficial to use Si, FeSi, and Fe scrap. As there is likely to be more impurities in these material, these must be tested and the processes likely have to be fine tuned according to the results.

Global warming potential is considered one of the most important impact categories and is one of the most commonly used. In this study, GWP is seen in both the CML-baseline method and the IPCC method, the latter being focused on solely on GWP. For Norway, the total GWP using the CML method were found to be 2.62, 2.21 and 1.65 kg CO₂ eq for FeSi, FeB using scrap Al, and FeSiAl respectively. For the same routes, the values were 2.64, 2.25, and 1.65 kg CO₂ eq using the IPCC method. The values for the IPCC method are generally slightly higher, due to different category indicators being used in the methods. For Spain, the total GWP using the CML method was 3.37, 2.90, and 2.11 kg CO₂ eq for FeSi, FeB using scrap Al, and FeSiAl, respectively, while IPCC method gives 3.38, 2.91, and 2.11 kg CO₂ eq.

Most of these emissions are caused by the Si and Fe-75 Si production. The main reason that FeSi route has a higher GWP is that a large amount of Fe-75Si is used, 0.603 kg. Even though Si production has a higher emission than Fe-75Si production as seen in Table 2.10, the FeB route uses a significantly lower amount of Si, 0.240kg, resulting in an overall lower GWP. With FeSiAl both having Fe-75Si as the raw material and using 0.347 kg, this route has the lowest GWP.

From the results it can be seen that producing the alloy in Spain always has a higher impact than producing it in Norway. The process is the same, and the difference comes from the electricity country mix only. In Norway, hydropower is the main source for electrical power and is considered low impact. Spain, on the other hand, has their fossil fuels as their main source of electrical power. However, the country has been investing in solar and wind power, which will reduce the impact of the electricity. This shows how much effect production in one country compared to another can have on the total environmental emissions. To reduce the impact, a country with low impact electricity consumption is better.

Although waste treatment has not been considered, it is still useful to look at the amount of waste created from each process. This gives an indication as to how much impact the waste treatment will have, although this will also depend on the type of waste treatment necessary. FeSi route creates the largest amount of slag, with 1.74 kg slag per kg FeSiB alloy. The FeB route has 1.62 kg of slag and 0.015 kg of dust from the aluminothermic production of Fe-20B. FeSiAl has the lowest waste amount, with 0.952 kg of slag. From this, the waste from the FeSiAl is expected to have the lowest impact from treatment based on the amount, but, as stated, it will depend on the type of treatment needed.

From an overall point of view, FeSiAl has the lowest impact in most impact categories, has the lowest GWP, and the least amount of waste. The impact of the process will be reduced when the FeSi industry shifts towards biofuels instead of fossil fuels. CO₂ capture and energy recovery will further reduce the impact. This indicates that the FeSiAl production route will give the lowest environmental impact, especially if the process takes place in Norway.

6.1 Accuracy

Data accuracy and trustworthiness is an important part of the an LCA. In this study, it has been challenging to find data, as the topic is currently under research and no information outside the THERMOBAT project has been found on the Fe-24Si-11B alloy itself. Because of this, many assumptions and simplification were done, which reduces the accuracy of the study.

The mining and enrichment of colemanite is mainly conducted in Turkey, and most papers are written in Turkish. As a result, only one literature review of these papers were found in English, and was the only material used for finding the inputs for this process. The paper did not include outputs, and outputs from combustion of fuels were found using statistical data. This means that other outputs, such as rock waste and other factors from the mining were not included.

Some inputs, were not in the Ecoinvent database. These materials had to either be substituted for different materials or excluded if they were expected to be low impact. This can affect the amount of materials needed, and simplifications had to be made when substituting.

Because many of the processes were created for this project, they do not have any data available. These processes had to be mass balanced based on stoichiometric values. Typically, this will be an underestimate of the amount of input materials needed, resulting in a lower impact than is likely to be in reality.

Another issue is the electricity. This is roughly estimated using energy balance in HSC chemistry, and is based on mass balance. The materials were heated to the chosen temperature, and expected to have a phase change. This does not include energy for holding temperature, energy loss from ovens, and other factors occurring in reality. This value is likely to be underestimated, and to be taken with a grain of salt.

As the production routes were still experimental at the start of this study, some of the temperatures are based on phase change diagrams alone and not experimental values or data. These are especially the production of Fe-41Si and production of Fe-22Si-23Al, and will likely be subject to change.

The heavy metals for the Si production was given for metallurgical grade Si only, Table 2.12. To simplify, 75 % of these values were used for the Fe-75Si production. However, when look at other emissions from the process, it can be seen that Fe-75Si does not have approximately 75 % that of Si. For SO_x, the value is in fact higher.

It should therefore be noted that this is simplification.

It is also worth noting that transport has not been considered in this study. There would be a fair difference between transport to Spain and Norway. When considering the production of the Fe-24Si-11B alloy only, it could be worth doing the production in Norway. This would mean materials would only need to be transported to Norway, where the production would take place. If the production were to take place in Spain, the raw materials for the Si and Fe-75Si would first be transported to Norway for production, then the products have to be transported to Spain. This adds a transport step. However, distance would also have to be considered. As the Fe-24Si-11B alloy is only one component of the thermal energy storage, the place of production will also depend on the production of the other parts. This topic would need further study.

Chapter 7

Conclusion

It was seen early that the FeB using primary Al route had the highest impact in most of the categories and was not the best candidate. As a result, it was not discussed in detail. The reason is because of the production of the primary Al. Using scrap Al, if possible, reduced the impact and made it more comparable to the FeSi and FeSiAl route, but still had a higher impact in many of the categories.

GWP was the impact discussed in most detail. Norway had impacts of 2.64, 2.25 and 1.65 kg CO₂ eq for FeSi, FeB using scrap Al, and FeSiAl using the IPCC method, while Spain had 3.38, 2.93, and 2.11 kg CO₂ eq. The CML method gave similar, but slightly lower values. From this it could be seen that the FeSiAl route had the lowest GWP.

FeSiAl turned out to have the lowest values in most of the impact categories and the least waste material. When looking at electricity, Norway has a lower impact in Spain. As a result, the FeSiAl production route in Norway will have the lowest impact of all the routes. To reduce the impact further, virgin materials can be swapped for scrap or recycled material, fossil fuels can be changed for biofuels, and CO₂ capture and energy recovery can be implemented.

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A Inventory of conventional mixes by Cathrine Nøstvold

Table A.1: Life cycle inventory of conventional mixes for silicon production by Cathrine Nøstvold [27].

		MIX85%	MIX90%	MIX95%
Product (F.U.)				
Silicon, metallurgical grade	ton	1.00	1.00	1.00
Avoided products				
Silica sand {GLO} market for APOS, U	kg	412.61	261.60	127.45
Electricity, medium voltage NO market for APOS, U	MJ	10 240.07	9 444.81	8 738.31
Inputs from nature				
Water, river, NO	m ³	47.28	45.20	43.45
Air	ton	50.46	46.26	42.53
Inputs from technosphere				
Silica sand {GLO} market for APOS, U	kg	2 710.57 +24.57	2 550.37 +23.24	2 408.06 +22.05
Coke {GLO} market for APOS, U	MJ	5 721.36	5 528.72	5 357.58
Hard coal {Europe, without Russia and Turkey} market for hard coal APOS, U	kg	766.05	740.25	717.34
Charcoal {GLO} market for APOS, U	kg	367.67	355.29	344.29
Wood chips, wet, measured as dry mass {Europe without Switzerland} market for APOS, U	kg	837.74	809.54	184.48
Graphite {GLO} market for APOS, U	kg	108.69	108.24	107.83
Quicklime, in pieces, loose {RoW} market for quicklime, in pieces, loose APOS, U	kg	2.42	2.04	1.71
Electricity, medium voltage {NO} market for APOS, U	MJ	44 886.99	42 234.18	39 877.43
Emissions to air				
Silicon dioxide (silica)	g	165.11	104.68	51.00

Carbon dioxide, fossil	kg	2 893.00	2 806.94	2 730.49
Carbon dioxide, biogenic	kg	2 179.80	2 106.41	2 041.20
Water	kg	1 614.79	1 544.98	1 482.96
Aluminium	g	122.88	117.31	112.37
Arsenic	mg	12.11	11.66	11.25
Boron	mg	19.37	18.40	17.54
Barium	mg	5.26	5.05	4.87
Beryllium	µg	82.16	78.51	75.28
Bismuth	µg	100.88	95.99	91.65
Calcium	g	180.08	169.90	160.85
Cadmium	mg	40.27	38.96	38.79
Cobalt	g	1.98	1.87	1.76
Chromium	µg	816.17	773.67	735.92
Copper	g	1.60	1.54	1.49
Iron	g	64.05	61.35	58.95
Mercury	µg	19.19	18.53	17.93
Potassium	g	1.73	1.65	1.59
Magnesium	g	15.59	15.05	14.56
Manganese	g	265.62	257.22	249.75
Molybdenum	mg	176.40	166.36	157.45
Sodium	mg	349.30	335.73	323.68
Nickel	µg	419.54	402.04	386.49
Phosphorus	g	4.68	4.52	4.37
Lead	mg	374.01	360.21	347.95
Antimony	mg	28.15	27.05	26.06
Scandium	µg	282.10	267.09	253.75
Selenium	mg	1.71	1.64	1.59
Tin	mg	68.16	65.28	62.72
Strontium	mg	619.37	592.91	569.40
Thallium	µg	248.09	233.96	221.40
Vanadium	µg	104.20	100.34	96.91
Tungsten	g	2.06	1.94	1.83
Zinc	g	8.71	8.41	8.14
Zirconium	µg	278.75	262.73	248.50
Sulfur oxides	kg	18.31	17.59	16.95
Nitrogen oxides	kg	45.56	42.87	40.48
Dinitrogen monoxide	g	81.34	76.53	72.26
Methane	g	238.62	224.52	211.99
Carbon monoxide	kg	5.55	5.22	4.93
PAH, polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons	kg	3.15	2.96	2.80
Hydrocarbons, chlorinated	ng	40.30	37.92	35.80

Emissions to water

PAH, polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons	mg	73.88	69.51	65.63
Suspended solids, unspecified	g	895.08	842.18	795.19
Cooling water	m ³	47.28	45.20	43.35

Waste to treatment

Slag from metallurgical grade silicon production {GLO} market for APOS, U	kg	113.21	107.08	101.63
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B CML results tables

B.1 Overall comparison

Table B.1: Results for the impact categories using the CML-IA baseline method when comparing the different production methods. A cut-off of 1 % was used.

Impact category	Unit	FeSi		Primary		Al scrap		FeSiAl	
		Norway	Spain	Al	FeB	Al	FeB	Norway	Spain
Abiotic depletion	kg Sb eq	1.61E-06	2.27E-06	9.17E-05	9.23E-05	8.03E-05	8.09E-05	1.3E-06	1.71E-06
Abiotic depletion (fossil fuels)	MJ	20.10256	28.87322	132.5862	140.6504	15.40418	23.46842	7.568963	13.02065
Global warming (GWP100a)	kg CO2 eq	2.623941	3.366214	14.90525	15.58621	2.214938	2.8959	1.647495	2.107848
Ozone layer depletion (ODP)	kg CFC-11 eq	5.15E-08	9.15E-08	4.09E-07	4.46E-07	7.73E-08	1.14E-07	2.23E-08	4.71E-08
Human toxicity	kg 1,4-DB eq	0.837544	1.102997	10.23997	10.4837	2.799716	3.043447	0.37588	0.54065
Fresh water aquatic ecotox.	kg 1,4-DB eq	0.504636	0.740999	10.63872	10.85614	1.682519	1.899935	0.213133	0.360114
Marine aquatic ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DB eq	1585.43	2758.259	38126.42	39206.65	2732.689	3812.917	998.4873	1728.756
Terrestrial ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DB eq	0.112243	0.113331	0.024574	0.02539	0.003137	0.003953	0.073911	0.074463
Photochemical oxidation	kg C2H4 eq	0.000318	0.000521	0.004734	0.00492	0.000519	0.000706	0.000127	0.000253
Acidification	kg SO2 eq	0.007918	0.013529	0.08645	0.091618	0.015322	0.02049	0.004459	0.007953
Eutrophication	kg PO4— eq	0.003826	0.005036	0.021089	0.0222	0.003495	0.004606	0.001785	0.002536

B.2 Abiotic depletion

Table B.2: Distribution of abiotic depletion for the different production routes. A cut-off of 1 % was used and all values are given in kg SB eq.

Process	FeSi Norway	FeSi Spain	Al scrap FeB Norway	Al scrap FeB Spain	FeSiAl Norway	FeSiAl Spain
Boric acid	-	-	7.93E-05	7.93E-05	-	-
Electricity Spain	-	9.47E-07	-	8.74E-07	-	5.91E-07
Iron pellet	7.05E-07	7.06E-07	2.6E-07	2.6E-07	8.04E-07	8.04E-07
Total	1.61E-06	2.27E-06	8.03E-05	8.09E-05	1.3E-06	1.71E-06

B.3 Abiotic depletion (fossil fuels)

Table B.3: Distribution of abiotic depletion for fossil fuels for the different production routes. A cut-off of 1 % was used and all values are given in MJ.

Process	FeSi Norway	FeSi Spain	Al scrap FeB Norway	Al scrap FeB Spain	FeSiAl Norway	FeSiAl Spain
Boric acid	-	-	7.62	7.62	0.00	-
Coke	6.36	6.37	1.93	1.93	2.10	2.10
Electricity Spain	-	9.09	-	8.39	0.00	5.67
Electricity Norway	0.61	0.25	0.45	0.12	0.40	0.18
Hard coal	12.07	12.09	3.66	3.66	3.96	3.96
Iron ore	-	-	0.83	0.83	0.00	-
Iron pellet	0.66	0.66	0.24	0.24	0.75	0.75
Silica sand	0.40	0.40	0.24	0.24	0.26	0.26
Total	20.10	28.87	15.40	23.47	7.57	13.02

B.4 GWP100a

Table B.4: Distribution of global warming potential for the different production routes. A cut-off of 1 % was used and all values are given in kg CO₂ eq.

Process	FeSi Norway	FeSi Spain	Al scrap FeB Norway	Al scrap FeB Spain	FeSiAl Norway	FeSiAl Spain
Boric acid	-	-	0.59	0.59	-	-
Coke	0.16	0.16	0.048	0.048	0.052	0.052
Electricity Spain	-	0.79	-	0.72	-	0.49
Electricity No	0.081	0.034	0.060	0.016	0.053	0.024
Fe-75Si - FeSi route	2.11	2.12	-	-	-	-
Fe-75Si - FeSiAl route	-	-	-	-	1.39	1.39
Hard coal	0.19	0.19	0.056	0.056	0.061	0.061
Iron pellet	0.050	0.050	0.019	0.019	0.057	0.057
Magnesium ox- ide	-	-	0.15	0.15	-	-
Silica sand	0.036	0.036	0.022	0.022	0.024	0.024
Silicon produced in Norway	-	-	1.20	1.20	-	-
Total	2.62	3.37	2.21	2.90	1.65	2.11

B.5 ODP

Table B.5: Distribution of ODP for the different production routes. A cut-off of 1 % was used and all values are given in kg CFC-11 eq.

Process	FeSi Norway	FeSi Spain	Al scrap FeB Norway	Al scrap FeB Spain	FeSiAl Norway	FeSiAl Spain
Boric acid	-	-	4.77E-08	4.77E-08	-	-
Coke	3.4E-08	3.41E-08	1.03E-08	1.03E-08	1.12E-08	1.12E-08
Electricity Spain	-	4.15E-08	-	3.83E-08	-	2.59E-08
Electricity Nor- way	2.77E-09	1.15E-09	2.06E-09	5.57E-10	1.83E-09	8.11E-10
Hard coal	8.56E-09	8.58E-09	2.59E-09	2.59E-09	2.81E-09	2.81E-09
Iron ore	-	-	9.29E-09	9.29E-09	-	-
Iron pellet	3.63E-09	3.63E-09	1.34E-09	1.34E-09	4.13E-09	4.13E-09
Silica sand	2.52E-09	2.52E-09	1.52E-09	1.52E-09	1.65E-09	1.65E-09
Total	5.15E-08	9.15E-08	7.73E-08	1.14E-07	2.23E-08	4.71E-08

B.6 Human toxicity

Table B.6: Distribution of human toxicity for the different production routes. A cut-off of 1 % was used and all values are given in kg 1.4-DB eq.

Process	FeSi Norway	FeSi Spain	Al scrap FeB Norway	Al scrap FeB Spain	FeSiAl Norway	FeSiAl Spain
Boric acid	-	-	2.46	2.46	-	-
Coke	0.48	0.48	0.15	0.15	0.16	0.16
Electricity Spain	-	0.31	-	0.28	-	0.19
Electricity Nor- way	0.074	0.031	0.055	0.015	0.049	0.022
Hard coal	0.16	0.16	0.050	0.050	0.054	0.054
Iron pellet	0.071	0.071	0.026	0.026	0.081	0.081
Total	0.84	1.10	2.80	3.04	0.38	0.54

B.7 Fresh water aquatic ecotoxicity

Table B.7: Distribution of fresh water aquatic ecotoxicity for the different production routes. A cut-off of 1 % was used and all values are given in kg 1.4-DB eq.

Process	FeSi Norway	FeSi Spain	Al scrap FeB Norway	Al scrap FeB Spain	FeSiAl Norway	FeSiAl Spain
Boric acid	-	-	1.41	1.41	-	-
Coke	0.15	0.15	0.046	0.046	0.050	0.050
Electricity Spain	-	0.27	-	0.25	-	0.17
Electricity Nor- way	0.053	0.022	0.039	0.011	0.035	0.015
Hard coal	0.26	0.26	0.080	0.080	0.086	0.086
Iron pellet	0.029	0.029	0.011	0.011	0.033	0.033
Magnesium ox- ide	-	-	0.075	0.075	-	-
Total	0.50	0.74	1.68	1.90	0.21	0.36

B.8 Marine aquatic ecotoxicity

Table B.8: Distribution of marine aquatic ecotoxicity for the different production routes. A cut-off of 1 % was used and all values are given in kg 1.4-DB eq.

Process	FeSi Norway	FeSi Spain	Al scrap FeB Norway	Al scrap FeB Spain	FeSiAl Norway	FeSiAl Spain
Boric acid	-	-	2064.30	2064.30	-	-
Coke	347.48	348.11	105.58	105.58	114.47	114.47
Electricity Spain	-	1225.31	-	1131.26	-	764.77
Electricity Nor- way	94.30	39.11	70.00	18.97	62.10	27.59
Hard coal	585.54	586.60	177.47	177.47	192.26	192.26
Iron pellet	523.14	524.10	192.81	192.81	596.61	596.61
Magnesium ox- ide	-	-	70.73	70.73	-	-
Total	1585.43	2758.26	2743.87	3824.10	998.49	1728.76

B.9 Terrestrial ecotoxicity

Table B.9: Distribution of terrestrial ecotoxicity for the different production routes. A cut-off of 1 % was used and all values are given in kg 1.4-DB eq.

Process	FeSi Norway	FeSi Spain	Al scrap FeB Norway	Al scrap FeB Spain	FeSiAl Norway	FeSiAl Spain
Boric acid	-	-	0.0024	0.0024	-	-
Fe-75Si - FeSi route	0.11	0.11	-	-	-	-
Fe-75Si - FeSiAl route	-	-	-	-	0.074	0.074
Total	0.11	0.11	-	-	0.074	0.074

B.10 Photochemical oxidation

Table B.10: Distribution of photochemical oxidation for the different production routes. A cut-off of 1 % was used and all values are given in kg C₂H₄ eq.

Process	FeSi Norway	FeSi Spain	Al scrap FeB Norway	Al scrap FeB Spain	FeSiAl Norway	FeSiAl Spain
Boric acid	-	-	3.61E-04	3.61E-04	-	-
Coke	1.90E-04	1.90E-04	5.77E-05	5.77E-05	6.25E-05	6.25E-05
Electricity Spain	-	2.09E-04	-	1.93E-04	-	1.30E-04
Electricity Norway	1.15E-05	4.76E-06	8.51E-06	2.31E-06	7.55E-06	3.36E-06
Hard coal	8.87E-05	8.88E-05	2.69E-05	2.69E-05	2.91E-05	2.91E-05
Iron ore	-	-	2.34E-05	2.34E-05	-	-
Iron pellet	1.75E-05	1.75E-05	6.44E-06	6.44E-06	1.99E-05	1.99E-05
Magnesium oxide	-	-	2.65E-05	2.65E-05	-	-
Silica sand	1.02E-05	1.02E-05	6.14E-06	6.14E-06	6.67E-06	6.67E-06
Total	3.18E-04	5.21E-04	5.19E-04	7.06E-04	1.27E-04	2.53E-04

B.11 Acidification

Table B.11: Distribution of acidification for the different production routes. A cut-off of 1 % was used and all values are given in kg SO₂ eq.

Process	FeSi Norway	FeSi Spain	Al scrap FeB Norway	Al scrap FeB Spain	FeSiAl Norway	FeSiAl Spain
Boric acid	-	-	0.010	0.010	-	-
Coke	1.04E-03	1.04E-03	3.17E-04	3.17E-04	3.44E-04	3.44E-04
Electricity Spain	-	5.72E-03	-	5.28E-03	-	3.57E-03
Electricity Norway	2.12E-04	8.81E-05	1.58E-04	4.27E-05	1.40E-04	6.22E-05
Fe-75Si - FeSi route	3.97E-03	3.97E-03	-	-	-	-
Fe-75Si - FeSiAl route	-	-	-	-	2.60E-03	2.60E-03
Hard coal	2.00E-03	2.00E-03	6.05E-04	6.05E-04	6.56E-04	6.56E-04
Iron ore	-	-	8.91E-04	8.91E-04	-	-
Iron pellet	4.61E-04	4.62E-04	1.70E-04	1.70E-04	5.26E-04	5.26E-04
Silica sand	2.32E-04	2.33E-04	1.41E-04	1.41E-04	1.53E-04	1.53E-04
Silicon produced in Norway	-	-	2.64E-03	2.64E-03	-	-
Total	7.92E-03	0.014	0.015	0.020	4.46E-03	7.95E-03

B.12 Eutrophication

Table B.12: Distribution of eutrophication for the different production routes. A cut-off of 1 % was used and all values are given in kg PO₄ eq.

Process	FeSi Norway	FeSi Spain	Al scrap FeB Norway	Al scrap FeB Spain	FeSiAl Norway	FeSiAl Spain
Boric acid	-	-	1.64E-03	1.64E-03	-	-
Coke	8.87E-04	8.89E-04	2.70E-04	2.70E-04	2.92E-04	2.92E-04
Electricity	-	1.28E-03	-	1.18E-03	-	7.99E-04
Electricity	1.31E-04	5.43E-05	9.71E-05	2.63E-05	8.61E-05	3.83E-05
Fe-75Si - FeSi route	1.03E-03	1.03E-03	-	-	-	-
Fe-75Si - FeSiAl route	-	-	-	-	6.77E-04	6.77E-04
Hard coal	1.59E-03	1.59E-03	4.81E-04	4.81E-04	5.22E-04	5.22E-04
Iron ore	-	-	1.34E-04	1.34E-04	-	-
Iron pellet	1.36E-04	1.36E-04	5.00E-05	5.00E-05	1.55E-04	1.55E-04
Silica sand	4.89E-05	4.90E-05	2.96E-05	2.96E-05	3.21E-05	3.21E-05
Silicon produced in Norway	-	-	6.86E-04	6.86E-04	-	-
Total	3.83E-03	5.04E-03	3.50E-03	4.61E-03	1.79E-03	2.54E-03

C ReCiPE results tables

C.1 Overall comparison

Table C.1: Results for the impact categories using the ReCiPE Endpoint method when comparing the different production methods. A cut-off of 1 % was used.

Damage category	Unit	FeSi		Primary		AI scrap		FeSiAl	
		Norway	Spain	Al	FeB	Norway	Spain	Norway	Spain
Human health	DALY	1.36E-05	1.55E-05	4.63E-05	4.81E-05	7.28E-06	9.09E-06	8.54E-06	9.76E-06
Ecosystems	species.yr	1.42E-08	1.79E-08	7.13E-08	7.47E-08	1.26E-08	1.61E-08	8.64E-09	1.1E-08
Resources	USD2013	0.058989	0.106235	0.563885	0.607408	0.095372	0.138895	0.030435	0.059858

C.2 Human health

Table C.2: Distribution of human health impact for the different production routes. A cut-off of 1 % was used and all values are given in DALY.

Process	FeSi Norway	FeSi Spain	Al scrap FeB Norway	Al scrap FeB Spain	FeSiAl Norway	FeSiAl Spain
Boric acid	-	-	3.58E-06	3.58E-06	-	-
Coke	8.31E-07	8.32E-07	2.52E-07	2.52E-07	2.74E-07	2.74E-07
Electricity Spain	-	2.14E-06	-	1.98E-06	-	1.34E-06
Electricity Nor- way	3.19E-07	1.32E-07	2.37E-07	6.41E-08	2.1E-07	9.33E-08
Fe-75Si - FeSi route	1.13E-05	1.13E-05	-	-	-	-
Fe-75Si - FeSiAl route	-	-	-	-	7.39E-06	7.39E-06
Hard coal	7.75E-07	7.76E-07	2.35E-07	2.35E-07	2.54E-07	2.54E-07
Iron pellet	2.75E-07	2.76E-07	1.01E-07	1.01E-07	3.14E-07	3.14E-07
Magnesium ox- ide	-	-	4.52E-07	4.52E-07	-	-
Silicon produced in Norway	-	-	2.06E-06	2.06E-06	-	-
Total	1.36E-05	1.55E-05	7.28E-06	9.09E-06	8.54E-06	9.76E-06

C.3 Ecosystems

Table C.3: Distribution of ecosystems impact for the different production routes. A cut-off of 1 % was used and all values are given in species.yr.

Process	FeSi Norway	FeSi Spain	Al scrap FeB Norway	Al scrap FeB Spain	FeSiAl Norway	FeSiAl Spain
Boric acid	-	-	4.99E-09	4.99E-09	-	-
Coke	1.08E-09	1.08E-09	3.27E-10	3.27E-10	3.54E-10	3.54E-10
Electricity Spain	-	3.99E-09	-	3.69E-09	-	2.49E-09
Electricity Norway	4.66E-10	1.93E-10	3.46E-10	9.38E-11	3.07E-10	1.36E-10
Fe-75Si - FeSi route	1.05E-08	1.05E-08	-	-	-	-
Fe-75Si - FeSiAl route	-	-	-	-	6.88E-09	6.88E-09
Hard coal	1.53E-09	1.53E-09	4.64E-10	4.64E-10	5.03E-10	5.03E-10
Iron ore	-	-	4.76E-10	4.76E-10	-	-
Iron pellet	3.15E-10	3.16E-10	1.16E-10	1.16E-10	3.59E-10	3.59E-10
Magnesium oxide	-	-	5.65E-10	5.65E-10	-	-
Silica sand	2.86E-10	2.86E-10	1.73E-10	1.73E-10	1.88E-10	1.88E-10
Silicon produced in Norway	-	-	5.11E-09	5.11E-09	-	-
Total	1.42E-08	1.79E-08	1.26E-08	1.61E-08	8.64E-09	1.1E-08

C.4 Resources

Table C.4: Distribution of resources impact for the different production routes. A cut-off of 1 % was used and all values are given in USD2013.

Process	FeSi Norway	FeSi Spain	Al scrap FeB Norway	Al scrap FeB Spain	FeSiAl Norway	FeSiAl Spain
Boric acid	-	-	0.058	0.058	-	-
Coke	0.014	0.014	0.0043	0.0043	0.0046	0.0046
Electricity Spain	-	0.049	-	0.045	-	0.031
Electricity Norway	0.0032	0.0013	0.0024	6.46E-04	0.0021	9.40E-04
Hard coal	0.028	0.028	0.0086	0.0086	0.0093	0.0093
Iron ore	-	-	0.014	0.014	-	-
Iron pellet	0.010	0.010	0.0038	0.0038	0.012	0.012
Silica sand	0.0029	0.0029	0.0018	0.0018	0.0019	0.0019
Total	0.059	0.11	0.10	0.14	0.030	0.060

D IPCC results tables

D.1 Overall comparison

Table D.1: Results for the impact categories using the IPCC method when comparing the different production methods. A cut-off of 1 % was used.

Impact category	FeSi		Primary		Primary		Al scrap		Al scrap		FeSiAl	
	Norway	Spain	Al	FeB	Al	FeB	Al	FeB	Norway	Spain	Norway	Spain
GWP100 - fossil	2.633321	3.371849	15.00402	15.68151	2.215065	2.215065	2.892554	2.892554	1.649776	2.10778	1.649776	2.10778
GWP100 - biogenic	0.002126	0.002426	0.015642	0.015917	0.004728	0.004728	0.005003	0.005003	0.001445	0.001631	0.001445	0.001631
GWP100 - land transformation	0.001332	0.007397	0.019691	0.025288	0.002015	0.002015	0.007612	0.007612	0.00092	0.004704	0.00092	0.004704

D.2 GWP100 - fossil

Table D.2: Distribution of fossil GWP100 for the different production routes. A cut-off of 1 % was used and all values are given in kg CO₂ eq.

Process	FeSi Norway	FeSi Spain	Al scrap FeB Norway	Al scrap FeB Spain	FeSiAl Norway	FeSiAl Spain
Boric acid	-	-	0.59	0.59	-	-
Coke	0.16	0.16	0.049	0.049	0.053	0.053
Electricity Spain	-	0.78	-	0.72	-	0.49
Electricity Norway	0.079	0.033	0.059	0.016	0.052	0.023
Fe-75Si - FeSi route	2.11	2.12	-	-	-	-
Fe-75Si - FeSiAl route	-	-	-	-	1.39	1.39
Hard coal	0.19	0.19	0.058	0.058	0.063	0.063
Iron pellet	0.050	0.050	0.019	0.019	0.057	0.057
Magnesium oxide	-	-	0.15	0.15	-	-
Silica sand	0.036	0.036	0.022	0.022	0.024	0.024
Silicon produced in Norway	-	-	1.20	1.20	-	-
Total	2.63	3.37	2.22	2.89	1.65	2.11

D.3 GWP100 - biogenic

Table D.3: Distribution of biogenic GWP100 for the different production routes. A cut-off of 1 % was used and all values are given in kg CO₂ eq.

Process	FeSi Norway	FeSi Spain	Al scrap FeB Norway	Al scrap FeB Spain	FeSiAl Norway	FeSiAl Spain
Boric acid	-	-	1.10E-03	1.10E-03	-	-
Electricity Spain	-	1.41E-03	-	1.31E-03	-	8.83E-04
Electricity Norway	1.91E-03	7.91E-04	1.41E-03	3.83E-04	1.25E-03	5.58E-04
Iron pellet	1.21E-04	1.21E-04	4.47E-05	4.47E-05	1.38E-04	1.38E-04
Lime	-	-	2.06E-03	2.06E-03	-	-
Total	2.13E-03	2.43E-03	4.74E-03	5.01E-03	1.44E-03	1.63E-03

D.4 GWP100 - land transformation

Table D.4: Distribution of land transformation GWP100 for the different production routes. A cut-off of 1 % was used and all values are given in kg CO₂ eq.

Process	FeSi Norway	FeSi Spain	Al scrap FeB Norway	Al scrap FeB Spain	FeSiAl Norway	FeSiAl Spain
Boric acid	-	-	1.02E-03	1.02E-03	-	-
Electricity Spain	-	6.38E-03	-	5.89E-03	-	3.98E-03
Electricity Nor- way	5.50E-04	2.28E-04	4.08E-04	1.11E-04	3.62E-04	1.61E-04
Hard coal	7.96E-05	7.97E-05	2.41E-05	2.41E-05	2.61E-05	2.61E-05
Iron ore	-	-	1.48E-04	1.48E-04	-	-
Iron pellet	1.08E-04	1.08E-04	3.97E-05	3.97E-05	1.23E-04	1.23E-04
Silica sand	5.28E-04	5.29E-04	3.20E-04	3.20E-04	3.47E-04	3.47E-04
Total	1.33E-03	7.40E-03	2.06E-03	7.66E-03	9.20E-04	4.70E-03

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